

BOUND STATES OF TWO-DIMENSIONAL MAGNETOEXCITONS TAKING INTO ACCOUNT THE RASHBA SPIN-ORBIT COUPLING

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Abstract

Molecular-type bound states of two-dimensional (2D) magnetoexcitons supplementarily subjected to the action of an external electric field perpendicular to the layer and parallel to a strong magnetic field are studied. The electron and hole wave functions have different numbers of the Landau quantization levels for different spin projections. The Rashba spin-orbit coupling (RSOC) is characterized by first-order chirality terms for electrons and third-order chirality terms for heavy holes in GaAs-type quantum wells. In this case, the external electric field gives rise to the nonparabolic dispersion law of heavy holes and a nonmonotonous dependence of their energy levels on the magnetic field strength. The spinor-type wave functions of electrons and holes for their lowest energy levels are used to construct the one- and two-magnetoexciton wave functions to determine their normalization conditions, and deduce the Hamiltonian of the Coulomb electron-electron interaction in the presence of the RSOC. It contains electron and hole imprint factors, the difference of which determines the affinities of the electron-hole pairs to interact between themselves. The average value of the Coulomb interaction Hamiltonian makes it possible to calculate the mean energy value per two pairs forming the molecule versus parameter α of the wave function, which determines the relative motion of two magnetoexcitons in the frame of the bound state. The next numerical calculations will show whether the stable bound state of the molecular type or the metastable bound state does exist.

Keywords: two-dimensional (2D) magnetoexcitons, Landau quantization levels, Rashba spin-orbit coupling, chirality, Coulomb interaction.

Rezumat

Au fost cercetate stările legate de tip molecular ale magnetoexcitonilor bi-dimensionali (2D) supuși suplimentar acțiunii câmpului electric extern perpendicular pe strat și paralel cu câmpul magnetic puternic. Funcțiile de undă asociate electronilor și golurilor au numere diferite ale nivelelor de cuantificare Landau pentru diferite proiecții de spin. Cuplarea spin-orbită de tip Rashba (RSOC) se caracterizează prin termeni de chiralitate de prim ordin pentru electroni și prin termeni de chiralitate de ordinul al treilea pentru golurile grele din gropile cuantice de tip GaAs. În acest caz, câmpul electric extern provoacă apariția dispersiei non-parabolice a golurilor grele și dependența non-monotonă a nivelelor de cuantificare de forța câmpului magnetic. Pentru a construi funcțiile de undă ale excitonului magnetic și ale bimagnetoexcitonului, pentru a determina condițiile de normalizare ale acestora și pentru a deduce Hamiltonianul interacțiunii

Coulombiene electron-electron în prezența RSOC, au fost selectate funcțiile de undă de tip spinor ale celor mai mici nivele energetice ale electronilor și golurilor. Ele conțin factori de imprimare ale electronilor și a golurilor, a căror diferență determină afinitățile perechilor e - h să interacționeze între ele. Valoarea medie a Hamiltonianului interacțiunii Coulombiene permite calcularea valorii medii a energiei a două perechi care formează molecula în dependență de parametrul funcției de undă α , care determină mișcarea relativă a doi magnetoexcitoni în cadrul stării legate. Următoarele calcule numerice vor arăta dacă există starea legată stabilă de tip molecular sau starea legată metastabilă.

Cuvinte cheie: magnetoexcitoni bi-dimensionali (2D), niveluri de cuantificare Landau, Cuplare spin-orbită de tip Rashba, chiralitate, interacțiune Coulombiană

1. Introduction

The interaction between two two-dimensional (2D) magnetoexcitons is the topic of our paper; it was discussed earlier in [1–4] in Landau gauge description with electrons and holes in different Landau quantization (LQ) states and with in-plane wave vectors $k = 0$. The hidden symmetry is characteristic of electron–hole (e – h) systems. It appears because the radii of the 2D cyclotron orbits of the electron and the hole do not depend on their effective masses m_e and m_h , but only on the magnetic length $l_0 = hc/(eB)$, depending on magnetic field strength B . If the electron and the hole are in the same Landau level state and have the same gyration point, then their orbits are overlapped and the magnetoexciton with center-of-mass in-plane wave vector $k_p = 0$ looks as a neutral object. The Coulomb interaction between two magnetoexcitons with wave vectors $k_p = 0$ vanishes. To obtain the interactions between them, it is necessary to consider the cases with $k_p \neq 0$ or be beyond the lowest Landau levels (LLLs) approximation. Two magnetoexcitons with dipole structures are represented in Fig. 1. They have opposite in-plane wave vector $\vec{k}_p$ and $-\vec{k}_p$ and electric dipoles $\vec{d}$ and $-\vec{d}$, because the resultant wave vector of the bound state is supposed to be equal to zero.

Fig. 1. Biexciton bound states of two 2D magnetoexcitons. The figure is reprinted from [5].

Each magnetoexciton consists of an electron and a hole situated on particular levels of the LQ with the quantum numbers, for example, $n_e(1)$ and $n_h(1)$ for the first exciton and $n_e(2)$ and $n_h(2)$ for the second exciton. Two excitons, the structure of which is characterized by the equalities $n_e(1) = n_e(2)$ and $n_h(1) = n_h(2)$, can be referred to as homogeneous excitons. In the opposite case $n_e(1) \neq n_e(2)$ and $n_h(1) \neq n_h(2)$, they are heterogeneous. In the intermediary case, at $n_e(1) = n_e(2)$, but $n_h(1) \neq n_h(2)$ or vice versa $n_e(1) \neq n_e(2)$, but $n_h(1) = n_h(2)$, these two magnetoexcitons can be considered as semihomogeneous.

The authors of [1] studied the interaction of 2D magnetoexcitons with the in-plane wave vector of $k = 0$ taking into account the effect of the excited Landau levels (ELs) and an external electric field perpendicular to the quantum well surface and parallel to the external magnetic field. It was shown that the account of the ELs gives rise to the repulsion between the spinless magnetoexcitons with $\dot{k}_{\parallel} = 0$ in the Fock approximation, with the interaction constant g decreasing inversely proportional to the magnetic field strength B ($g(0) \sim 1/B$). In the presence of a perpendicular electric field, the Rashba spin-orbit coupling (RSOC), Zeeman splitting, and nonparabolicity of the heavy-hole dispersion law affect the LQ of the electrons and the holes. They move along the new cyclotron orbits, change their Coulomb interactions, and cause the interaction between 2D magnetoexcitons with $\dot{k}_{\parallel} = 0$. The changes of the Coulomb interactions caused by the electrons and the holes moving with new cyclotron orbits are characterized by some coefficients, which, in the absence of an electric field, turn to be unity. They can be referred to as imprints. The differences between these coefficients of the e-h pairs forming the magnetoexcitons determine their affinities to the interactions. The interactions between the homogeneous, semihomogeneous, and heterogeneous magnetoexcitons forming the symmetric states with the same signs of their affinities are attractive, whereas in the case of different sign affinities they are repulsive. In heterogeneous asymmetric states, the interactions have opposite signs compared with the symmetric states. In all these cases, the interaction constant g exhibits the following dependence: $g(0) \sim 1/\sqrt{B}$.

The authors of [2] studied the possible existence of 2D bimagnetoexcitons and metastable bound states formed by two magnetoexcitons with opposite in-plane wave vectors $\dot{k}_p$ and $-\dot{k}_p$. Magnetoexcitons involved in the formation of molecules look as two electric dipoles with the arms oriented in-plane perpendicular to the respective wave vectors and with the length of the arms $d = kl_0^2$, where l_0 is the magnetic length. Two antiparallel dipoles moving with equal, yet antiparallel, wave vectors have the possibility of moving with equal probability in any direction of the plane, which is determined by the trial wave function of relative motion $\varphi_n(|\dot{k}_p|)$ depending on modulus k . The magnetoexcitons are composed of electrons and holes situated on the LLLs with the cyclotron energies greater than the binding energy of the 2D Wannier-Mott exciton. The description was made in Landau gauge. The spin states of two electrons were chosen in the form of antisymmetric or symmetric combinations with parameter $\eta = \pm 1$. The effective spins of two heavy holes were combined in the same resultant spinor states as the spin of the electrons. Since the projections of the both spinor states with $\eta = \pm 1$ are equal to zero, the influence of the Zeeman splitting effect vanishes. In the case of trial wave function

$\varphi_2(k) = (8\alpha^3)^{1/2} k^2 l_0^2 e^{-\alpha k^2 l_0^2}$, the maximal density of the magnetoexcitons in the momentum space is concentrated on the in-plane ring with radius $k_r = 1/(\sqrt{\alpha} l_0)$.

Fig. 2. Spin structure of two magnetoexcitons. The figure is reprinted from [5].

In [3] and [4], four different spin structures of two electrons and two holes situated on the LLLs were taken into account to study possible bound states of the 2D magnetic biexciton composed of two magnetoexcitons with opposite wave vectors and antiparallel dipole moments. The singlet and triplet states of the spins of two electrons and two holes separately, as well as two para- and two ortho-magnetoexcitons, were considered. They are represented in Fig. 2. In the first version, correlations between the spins of two homogeneous particles are supposed; in the second version, the resultant spin of each e-h pair is formed. In the calculations of the binding energy, only the first-order Coulomb electron-electron interaction was taken into account. Figure 3 shows the Feynman diagrams describing (a) the direct and (b) exchange electron-electron interaction.

Fig. 3. Feynman diagrams describing (a) the direct and (b) exchange Coulomb electron–electron interactions in the frame of the metastable bound state of two magnetoexcitons. The figure is reprinted from [5].

General expressions describing the binding energy of the bound states and the normalization conditions characterized by the effective spin parameter $\eta = \pm 1, \pm 2$ for the respective wave functions were derived. The general expression in the case of two e–h pairs in the absence of the RSOC and the average value of the Coulomb interaction in the absence of the RSOC are represented below.

$$E_{Bimex} = \frac{\langle \psi_{Bimex}(0, \eta) | H_{Coul}^{LLL} | \psi_{Bimex}(0, \eta) \rangle}{\langle \psi_{Bimex}(0, \eta) | \psi_{Bimex}(0, \eta) \rangle}$$

$$\langle \psi_{Bimex}(0, \eta) | H_{Coul}^{LLL} | \psi_{Bimex}(0, \eta) \rangle = \left\langle \begin{array}{l} \text{Feynman diagrams with} \\ \text{even numbers} \\ \text{of intersections} \end{array} \right\rangle + \eta \left\langle \begin{array}{l} \text{Feynman diagrams with} \\ \text{odd numbers} \\ \text{of intersections} \end{array} \right\rangle.$$

$$\langle \psi_{Bimex}(0, \eta) | \psi_{Bimex}(0, \eta) \rangle = 2(1 - \eta L_n(\alpha))$$

$\eta=1$	triplet-triplet and
$\eta=-1$	singlet-singlet spin structures of 2e+2h
$\eta=1/2$	ortho-ortho and
$\eta=-1/2$	para-para magnetoexcitons

In the second section of the paper, we will take into account, for the very beginning, the RSOC between the orbital and spin degree of freedom for electrons and holes using their spinor-type wave functions. On this base, the Hamiltonian of the Coulomb electron–electron interaction will be deduced. It contains imprint coefficients $S_e(\dot{Q})$ and $S_h(\dot{Q})$ multiplying the usual constant of the Coulomb interaction $W(\dot{Q})$ as follows: $W(\dot{Q})S_e^2(\dot{Q})$, $W(\dot{Q})S_h^2(\dot{Q})$, and $W(\dot{Q})S_e(\dot{Q})S_h(\dot{Q})$ for electron–electron, hole–hole, and e–h interactions, respectively. The difference $S_e(\dot{Q}) - S_h(\dot{Q})$ of the imprint coefficients determines the electron affinity of the e–h pair to interact with other charged particles. The average value of the Hamiltonian calculated with the trial wave function will be deduced. In the third section, these average values will be analyzed to elucidate the effect of the RSOC. The fourth section is the conclusions.

2. Wave Functions and Hamiltonian of the Coulomb Electron–Electron Interaction

In our calculations, we use the Landau gauge description, because it permits characterizing the wave functions of electrons and holes on their states of the LQ by wave vectors p and q as the quantum numbers. As a consequence, the wave functions of 2D magnetoexcitons and their creation and annihilation operators can be characterized by 2D wave vectors $\overset{\perp}{k}_p(k_x, k_y)$ as quantum numbers. Wave vector $\overset{\perp}{k}_p$ as a quantum number most properly describes the motions of the magnetoexcitons and especially their relative motions in the frame of the bound states, which are the main goal of our study.

The spinor-type wave functions of 2D electrons and holes under the action of strong magnetic and electric fields both perpendicular to the layer, giving rise to the LQ in the presence of the RSOC, were deduced in [5]. The electrons with two spin projections $s_z^e = \pm 1/2$ in the conduction band with first-order chirality terms were described by Rashba in [6]. The heavy holes in the GaAs-type quantum wells (QWs) are characterized by third-order chirality terms and the nonparabolic dispersion law induced as the RSOC by the electric field. In the Landau gauge description, the lower energy electron and hole wave functions look as follows [5]:

$$\begin{aligned} |\Psi_e(R_1, \overset{\perp}{r})\rangle &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{L_x}} e^{ipx} \begin{vmatrix} a_0^- \varphi_0 \left(\frac{y}{l_0} - pl_0 \right) \\ b_1^- \varphi_1 \left(\frac{y}{l_0} - pl_0 \right) \end{vmatrix}; \quad |a_0^-|^2 + |b_1^-|^2 = 1, \\ |\Psi_h(\varepsilon_3^-, \overset{\perp}{r})\rangle &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{L_x}} e^{iqx} \begin{vmatrix} c_3^- \varphi_3 \left(\frac{y}{l_0} + ql_0 \right) \\ d_0^- \varphi_0 \left(\frac{y}{l_0} + ql_0 \right) \end{vmatrix}; \quad |c_3^-|^2 + |d_0^-|^2 = 1. \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

They are characterized by unidimensional wave vectors p and q and different numbers of the LQ levels at different spin projections. Normalization coefficients a_0^- , b_1^- , c_3^- , and d_0^- depend on magnetic and electric field strengths [5].

The 2D magnetoexcitons are formed by e–h pairs with the electron in spinor state R_1 and the hole in spinor state ε_3^- . The creation and annihilation Fermi operators in these states are denoted as $a_{R_1, p}^\dagger$, $a_{R_1, p}$, $b_{\varepsilon_3^-, q}^\dagger$, $b_{\varepsilon_3^-, q}$, respectively. It was determined in [7] that, in the second quantization representation, the wave function of the 2D magnetoexciton and the respective creation operator $\Psi_{ex}^\dagger(F_1, \overset{\perp}{k}_p)$ look as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} |\Psi_{ex}(F_1, \overset{\perp}{k}_p)\rangle &= \hat{\Psi}_{ex}^\dagger(F_1, \overset{\perp}{k}_p)|0\rangle, \\ \hat{\Psi}_{ex}^\dagger(F_1, \overset{\perp}{k}_p) &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \sum_t e^{ik_y t l_0^2} a_{R_1, t + \frac{k_x}{2}}^\dagger b_{\varepsilon_3^-, -t + \frac{k_x}{2}}^\dagger, \quad N = \frac{S}{2\pi l_0^2}, \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $|0\rangle$ is the ground state wave function, N is the degeneracy of the electron and hole LQ

levels, S is the layer surface area, and l_0 is the magnetic length.

Now we will introduce a two-magnetoexciton wave function describing the bound state of molecular type of two 2D magnetoexcitons with opposite wave vectors $\mathbf{k}_p$ and $-\mathbf{k}_p$ and with relative motion described by the trial wave function $\varphi_n(\mathbf{k}_p)$. This biexciton-type wave function with the resultant wave vector equal to zero has the form

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \Psi_{bimex}(\varphi_n, 0) \right\rangle &= \frac{1}{N^{3/2}} \sum_{\mathbf{k}_p} \varphi_n(\mathbf{k}_p) \sum_{s,t} e^{ik_y(t-s)l_0^2} a_{R_1, t + \frac{k_x}{2}}^\dagger a_{R_1, s - \frac{k_x}{2}}^\dagger \times \\ &\times b_{\varepsilon_3^-, -s - \frac{k_x}{2}}^\dagger b_{\varepsilon_3^-, -t + \frac{k_x}{2}}^\dagger |0\rangle; \quad \frac{1}{N} \sum_{\mathbf{k}_p} |\varphi_n(\mathbf{k}_p)|^2 = 1. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The trial wave functions of relative motion $\varphi_n(\mathbf{k}_p)$ are written in the momentum representation. One of them was chosen in the form of $\varphi_2(\mathbf{k}_p) = (8\alpha^3)^{1/2} (k_p l_0)^2 e^{-\alpha(k_p l_0)^2}$ with variational parameter α and with the maximum value on the in-plane ring with radius $k_r = 1/(\sqrt{\alpha} l_0)$. It is minimal at point $\mathbf{k}_p = 0$, where the magnetoexcitons do not interact due to the hidden symmetry. The normalization condition for function (3) looks as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \Psi_{bimex}(\varphi_n, 0) | \Psi_{bimex}(\varphi_n, 0) \rangle &= 2(1 - L_n(\alpha)), \\ L_n(\alpha) &= \sum_{\mathbf{k}} \sum_{\mathbf{k}'} \varphi_n^*(\mathbf{k}') \varphi_n(\mathbf{k}) e^{iz_3 \sin t_3} = \int_0^\infty x dx \varphi_n(x) \int_0^\infty y dy \varphi_n(y) J_0(xy), \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{k} = k(\cos \varphi, \sin \varphi)$, $\mathbf{k}' = k'(\cos \psi, \sin \psi)$, $z_3 = k k' l_0^2$, $t_3 = \psi - \varphi$, and $J_0(xy)$ is the Bessel function. In the case of $\varphi_2(x) = (8\alpha^3)^{1/2} x^2 e^{-\alpha x^2}$, the overlapping integral equals to

$$L_2 = \frac{\left(2\alpha^2 - \frac{1}{2}\right)}{\left(\alpha + \frac{1}{4\alpha}\right)^3} = \frac{32\alpha^3(4\alpha^2 - 1)}{(4\alpha^2 + 1)^3}. \quad (5)$$

The Hamiltonian of the electron–electron Coulomb interaction taking into account the RSOC looks as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} H_{Coul} &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\mathbf{Q}} \left\{ W_{e-e}(\mathbf{R}_1; \mathbf{Q}) \left[\hat{\rho}_e(\mathbf{R}_1; \mathbf{Q}) \hat{\rho}_e(\mathbf{R}_1; -\mathbf{Q}) - \hat{N}_e(\mathbf{R}_1) \right] + \right. \\ &+ W_{h-h}(\varepsilon_3^-; \mathbf{Q}) \left[\hat{\rho}_h(\varepsilon_3^-; \mathbf{Q}) \hat{\rho}_h(\varepsilon_3^-; -\mathbf{Q}) - \hat{N}_h(\varepsilon_3^-) \right] - \\ &\left. - 2W_{e-h}(\mathbf{R}_1, \varepsilon_3^-; \mathbf{Q}) \hat{\rho}_e(\mathbf{R}_1; \mathbf{Q}) \hat{\rho}_h(\varepsilon_3^-; -\mathbf{Q}) \right\}, \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
 W_{e-e}(R_1; \vec{Q}) &= W(\vec{Q}) S_e^2(R_1; \vec{Q}), \quad W(\vec{Q}) = \frac{2\pi e^2}{\varepsilon_0 S |\vec{Q}|} e^{-\frac{Q^2 l_0^2}{2}}; \\
 W_{h-h}(\varepsilon_3^-; \vec{Q}) &= W(\vec{Q}) S_h^2(\varepsilon_3^-; \vec{Q}); \\
 W_{e-h}(R_1, \varepsilon_3^-; \vec{Q}) &= W(\vec{Q}) S_e(R_1; \vec{Q}) S_h(\varepsilon_3^-; \vec{Q}); \\
 S_e(R_1; \vec{Q}) &= \left(|a_0^-|^2 A_{0,0}(\vec{Q}) + |b_1^-|^2 A_{1,1}(\vec{Q}) \right); \\
 S_h(\varepsilon_3^-; \vec{Q}) &= \left(|d_0^-|^2 A_{0,0}(\vec{Q}) + |c_3^-|^2 A_{3,3}(\vec{Q}) \right), \\
 A_{0,0}(\vec{Q}) &= 1, \quad A_{1,1}(\vec{Q}) = 1 - \frac{Q^2 l_0^2}{2}, \quad A_{3,3}(\vec{Q}) = 1 - \frac{3}{2} Q^2 l_0^2 + \frac{3}{8} Q^4 l_0^4 - \frac{1}{48} Q^6 l_0^6.
 \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

The average value of the Hamiltonian equals to

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\langle \Psi_{bimex}(\varphi_2, 0) | \hat{H}_{Coul} | \Psi_{bimex}(\varphi_2, 0) \rangle = \\
 &= -\frac{4}{N} \sum_{\vec{Q}} \sum_{\vec{\chi}} W(\vec{Q}) S_e(\vec{Q}) S_h(\vec{Q}) \varphi_2^*(\vec{\chi}) \varphi_2(\vec{Q} - \vec{\chi}) + \\
 &+ \frac{4}{N} \sum_{\vec{Q}, \vec{\chi}} W(\vec{Q}) \left(\frac{S_e^2(\vec{Q}) + S_h^2(\vec{Q})}{2} \right) \varphi_2^*(\vec{\chi}) \varphi_2(\vec{Q} - \vec{\chi}) e^{iz_2 \sin t_2} - \\
 &- \frac{4}{N} \sum_{\vec{Q}, \vec{\chi}} W(\vec{Q}) S_e(\vec{Q}) S_h(\vec{Q}) |\varphi_2(\vec{\chi})|^2 \cos(z_2 \sin t_2) - \\
 &- \frac{4}{N^2} \sum_{\vec{Q}, \vec{\chi}, \vec{k}} W(\vec{Q}) \left(\frac{S_e^2(\vec{Q}) + S_h^2(\vec{Q})}{2} \right) \varphi_2^*(\vec{\chi}) \varphi_2(\vec{k}) \exp[iz_1 \sin t_1 + iz_2 \sin t_2 + iz_3 \sin t_3] + \\
 &+ \frac{4}{N^2} \sum_{\vec{Q}, \vec{\chi}, \vec{k}} W(\vec{Q}) S_e(\vec{Q}) S_h(\vec{Q}) \varphi_2^*(\vec{\chi}) \varphi_2(\vec{k}) [\cos(iz_2 \sin t_2) \cos(iz_3 \sin t_3) + \\
 &+ \cos(iz_1 \sin t_1) \cos(iz_3 \sin t_3)].
 \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

Here, the following denotations were introduced

$$\begin{aligned}
 z_1 &= kQl_0^2, \quad z_2 = \chi Ql_0^2, \quad z_3 = k\chi l_0^2, \quad t_1 = (\varphi - \theta), \quad t_2 = (\theta - \psi), \quad t_3 = (\psi - \varphi); \\
 \vec{Q} &= Q(\cos \theta, \sin \theta); \quad \vec{k} = k(\cos \varphi, \sin \varphi); \quad \vec{\chi} = \chi(\cos \psi, \sin \psi).
 \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

The five components MS_i with $i = 1, 2, \dots, 5$ of the average value (8) were calculated as follows. First of all, the summing up on variables $\vec{k}$ and $\vec{\chi}$ was effectuated neglecting the RSOC terms. It was succeeded by the integration on the variable $y = Ql_0$ including the imprint coefficients $S_e(\vec{Q})$ and

$S_h(\hat{Q})$.

First of all, we will study the energy components of the metastable bound state without RSOC with $S_e(Q) = S_h(Q) = 1$. The first energy component MS_1 looks as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 MS_1 &= -\frac{4}{N} \sum_{\vec{Q}, \vec{\chi}} W(\vec{Q}) \phi_2^*(\vec{\chi}) \phi_2(\vec{Q} - \vec{\chi}) = \\
 &= -\frac{32\alpha^3 e^2}{\varepsilon_0 l_0} \int_0^\infty dy e^{-\frac{y^2}{2}} \int_0^\infty dx x^3 e^{-\alpha x^2} \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} d\theta \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} d\psi \left[x^2 + y^2 - 2xy \cos(\theta - \psi) \right] \times \\
 &\times e^{-\alpha(x^2 + y^2 - 2xy \cos(\theta - \psi))} = -\frac{32\alpha^3 e^2}{\varepsilon_0 l_0} \int_0^\infty dy e^{-\frac{y^2}{2}} \int_0^\infty dx x^3 e^{-\alpha x^2} \left[(x^2 + y^2) e^{-\alpha(x^2 + y^2)} \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} d\theta \times \right. \\
 &\times \left. \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} d\psi e^{2\alpha xy \cos(\theta - \psi)} - 2xy e^{-\alpha(x^2 + y^2)} \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} d\theta \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} d\psi \cos(\theta - \psi) e^{2\alpha xy \cos(\theta - \psi)} \right] = \\
 &= -\frac{32\alpha^3 e^2}{\varepsilon_0 l_0} \int_0^\infty dy e^{-\frac{y^2}{2}} \int_0^\infty dx x^3 e^{-\alpha x^2} \left[(x^2 + y^2) e^{-\alpha(x^2 + y^2)} I_0(2\alpha xy) - \right. \\
 &\left. - 2xy e^{-\alpha(x^2 + y^2)} \frac{\partial}{\partial(2\alpha xy)} I_0(2\alpha xy) \right] = \\
 &= -\frac{32\alpha^3 e^2}{\varepsilon_0 l_0} \int_0^\infty dy e^{-y^2 \left(\frac{1}{2} + \alpha\right)} \int_0^\infty dx x^3 (x^2 + y^2) e^{-2\alpha x^2} I_0(2\alpha xy) + \\
 &+ \frac{64\alpha^3 e^2}{\varepsilon_0 l_0} \int_0^\infty dy y e^{-y^2 \left(\frac{1}{2} + \alpha\right)} \int_0^\infty dx x^4 e^{-2\alpha x^2} I_1(2\alpha xy). \tag{10}
 \end{aligned}$$

Here, we took into account that $dI_0(z)/dz = I_1(z)$, as well as the relations:

$$\begin{aligned}
 e^{z \cos t} &= I_0(z) + 2 \sum_{k=1}^\infty I_k(z) \cos kt; \quad \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} d\theta \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} d\psi e^{2\alpha xy \cos(\theta - \psi)} = I_0(2\alpha xy); \\
 \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} d\theta \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} d\psi \cos(\theta - \psi) e^{2\alpha xy \cos(\theta - \psi)} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial(2\alpha xy)} \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} d\theta \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} dx e^{2\alpha xy \cos(\theta - \psi)} = \\
 &= \frac{\partial I_0(2\alpha xy)}{\partial(2\alpha xy)} = I_1(2\alpha xy). \tag{11}
 \end{aligned}$$

The sum MS_1 can be transcribed in the form

$$\begin{aligned}
 MS_1 &= -\frac{32\alpha^3 e^2}{\varepsilon_0 l_0} \int_0^\infty dy e^{-y^2 \left(\frac{1}{2} + \alpha\right)} \int_0^\infty dx x^5 e^{-\alpha x^2} I_0(2\alpha xy) - \frac{32\alpha^3 e^2}{\varepsilon_0 l_0} \int_0^\infty dy y^2 e^{-y^2 \left(\frac{1}{2} + \alpha\right)} \int_0^\infty dx x^3 e^{-2\alpha x^2} \times \\
 &\times I_0(2\alpha xy) + \frac{64\alpha^3 e^2}{\varepsilon_0 l_0} \int_0^\infty dy y e^{-y^2 \left(\frac{1}{2} + \alpha\right)} \int_0^\infty dx x^4 e^{-2\alpha x^2} I_1(2\alpha xy). \tag{12}
 \end{aligned}$$

We now take into account the integrals [8, 9]:

$$\int_0^{\infty} dx x e^{-px^2} I_0(cx) = \frac{1}{2p} e^{\frac{c^2}{4p}}; \int_0^{\infty} dx x^5 e^{-px^2} I_0(cx) = \frac{\partial^2}{\partial p^2} \left(\frac{1}{2p} e^{\frac{c^2}{4p}} \right) = e^{\frac{c^2}{4p}} \left(\frac{1}{p^3} + \frac{c^2}{2p^4} + \frac{c^4}{32p^5} \right);$$

$$\int_0^{\infty} dx x^4 e^{-px^2} I_1(cx) = \frac{d^2}{dp^2} \int_0^{\infty} dx e^{-px^2} I_1(cx) = \frac{d^2}{dp^2} \left[e^{\frac{c^2}{4p}} - 1 \right] \frac{1}{c} = \left(\frac{c^1}{2p^3} + \frac{c^3}{16p^4} \right) e^{\frac{c^2}{4p}}. \quad (13)$$

They lead to the following results:

$$\int_0^{\infty} dx x^3 e^{-2\alpha x^2} I_0(2\alpha xy) = e^{\frac{\alpha y^2}{2}} \left(\frac{1}{8\alpha^2} + \frac{y^2}{16\alpha} \right); \int_0^{\infty} dx x^5 e^{-2\alpha x^2} I_0(2\alpha xy) = e^{\frac{\alpha y^2}{2}} \left(\frac{1}{8\alpha^3} + \frac{y^2}{8\alpha^2} + \frac{y^4}{64\alpha} \right);$$

$$\int_0^{\infty} dx x^4 I_1(2\alpha xy) e^{-2\alpha x^2} = e^{\frac{\alpha y^2}{2}} \left(\frac{y^2}{4\alpha} + \frac{y^4}{16} \right) \frac{1}{2\alpha y} = e^{\frac{\alpha y^2}{2}} \left(\frac{y}{8\alpha y^2} + \frac{y^3}{32\alpha} \right). \quad (14)$$

The last but one final expression looks as follows:

$$MS_1 = -\frac{4}{N} \sum_{\vec{Q}, \vec{\chi}} W(\vec{Q}) \varphi_2^*(\vec{\chi}) \varphi_2(\vec{Q} - \vec{\chi}) = -\frac{e^2}{\varepsilon_0 l_0} \int_0^{\infty} dy e^{-\frac{y^2}{2}(1+2\alpha)} \left(4 + 8\alpha y^2 + \frac{5}{2} y^4 \alpha^2 \right) +$$

$$+ \frac{4\alpha^2 e^2}{\varepsilon_0 l_0} \int_0^{\infty} dy y e^{-\frac{y^2}{2}(1+2\alpha)} (4y^2 + \alpha y^4) \frac{1}{2\alpha y} = -\frac{e^2}{\varepsilon_0 l_0} \int_0^{\infty} dy e^{-\frac{y^2}{2}(1+2\alpha)} \left(4 + \frac{1}{2} \alpha^2 y^4 \right). \quad (15)$$

It will be generalized taking into account the RSOC and supplementarily introducing the functions $S_e(\vec{Q})$, $S_h(\vec{Q}) \neq 1$ in the integrand.

The second component determining the energy of the metastable bound state is described by the expression

$$MS_2 = -\frac{4}{N} \sum_{\vec{Q}, \vec{\chi}} W(\vec{Q}) |\varphi_2(\vec{\chi})|^2 \cos(z_2 \sin t_2), \quad (16)$$

with $z_2 = \chi Q l_0^2$ and $t_2 = \theta - \psi$. It can be calculated taking into account the following relations [9, 10]:

$$e^{iz \sin t} = J_0(z) + 2 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} [J_{2k}(z) \cos 2kt + i J_{2k-1}(z) \sin(2k-1)t];$$

$$\cos(z \sin t) = J_0(z) + 2 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} J_{2k}(z) \cos 2kt;$$

$$\sin(z \sin t) = 2 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} J_{2k-1}(z) \sin(2k-1)t. \quad (17)$$

Expression (16) can be transcribed in the form

$$\begin{aligned}
 MS_2 &= -\frac{4e^2}{\varepsilon_0 l_0} \int_0^\infty dy e^{-\frac{y^2}{2}} \int_0^\infty dx x |\varphi_2(x)|^2 \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} d\theta \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} d\psi \times \\
 &\times \cos(z_2 \sin t_2) = -\frac{4e^2}{\varepsilon_0 l_0} \int_0^\infty dy e^{-\frac{y^2}{2}} \int_0^\infty dx x |\varphi_2(x)|^2 J_0(xy) = \\
 &= -\frac{32\alpha^3 e^2}{\varepsilon_0 l_0} \int_0^\infty dy e^{-\frac{y^2}{2}} \int_0^\infty dx x^5 e^{-2\alpha x^2} J_0(xy) = \\
 &= -\frac{4e^2}{\varepsilon_0 l_0} \int_0^\infty dy e^{-y^2 \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{8\alpha}\right)} \left[1 - \frac{y^2}{4\alpha} + \frac{y^4}{128\alpha^2} \right], \quad y = Ql_0.
 \end{aligned} \tag{18}$$

Here, the following integral was used [9]:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \int_0^\infty dx x^5 e^{-px^2} J_0(xy) &= \frac{\partial^2}{\partial p^2} \int_0^\infty dx x e^{-px^2} J_0(xy) = \\
 &= \frac{\partial^2}{\partial p^2} \left(\frac{1}{2p} e^{-\frac{y^2}{4p}} \right) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{2}{p^3} - \frac{y^2}{p^4} + \frac{y^4}{16p^5} \right) e^{-\frac{y^2}{4p}},
 \end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

$$p = 2\alpha.$$

The third component looks as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 MS_3 &= \frac{4}{N} \sum_{\vec{Q}, \vec{\chi}} W(\vec{Q}) \varphi_2^*(\vec{\chi}) \varphi_2(\vec{Q} - \vec{\chi}) e^{iz_2 \sin t_2}; \\
 \varphi_2(\vec{\chi}) &= (8\alpha^3)^{1/2} (\vec{\chi} l_0)^2 e^{-\alpha(\vec{\chi} l_0)^2}, \quad z_2 = \chi Q l_0^2, \quad t_2 = \theta - \psi.
 \end{aligned} \tag{20}$$

Introducing function $\varphi_2(\vec{\chi})$ into expression (20), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 MS_3 &= \frac{32\alpha^3 e^2}{\varepsilon_0 l_0} \int_0^\infty dy e^{-y^2 \left(\frac{1}{2} + \alpha\right)} \int_0^\infty dx x^3 e^{-2\alpha x^2} (x^2 + y^2) \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} d\theta \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} d\psi \times \\
 &\times e^{2\alpha xy \cos(\theta - \psi)} e^{ixy \sin(\theta - \psi)} - \frac{64\alpha^3 e^2}{\varepsilon_0 l_0} \int_0^\infty dy y e^{-y^2 \left(\frac{1}{2} + \alpha\right)} \int_0^\infty dx x^4 e^{-2\alpha x^2} \times \\
 &\times \cos(\theta - \psi) e^{2\alpha xy \cos(\theta - \psi)} e^{ixy \sin(\theta - \psi)} = \\
 &= \frac{32\alpha^3 e^2}{\varepsilon_0 l_0} \int_0^\infty dy e^{-y^2 \left(\frac{1}{2} + \alpha\right)} \int_0^\infty dx x^3 e^{-2\alpha x^2} (x^2 + y^2) [I_0(2\alpha xy) \cdot J_0(xy) + \\
 &+ 2 \sum_{k=1}^\infty [I_{2k}(2\alpha xy) \cdot J_{2k}(xy)] - \frac{64\alpha^3 e^2}{\varepsilon_0 l_0} \int_0^\infty dy y e^{-y^2 \left(\frac{1}{2} + \alpha\right)} \int_0^\infty dx x^4 e^{-2\alpha x^2} \times \\
 &\times \frac{\partial}{\partial(2\alpha xy)} [I_0(2\alpha xy) \cdot J_0(xy) + 2 \sum_{k=1}^\infty [I_{2k}(2\alpha xy) \cdot J_{2k}(xy)]].
 \end{aligned} \tag{21}$$

The encountered integrals were calculated as follows [10]:

$$\int_0^{\infty} dx x^3 e^{-2\alpha x^2} I_0(2\alpha xy) J_0(xy) = -\frac{\partial}{\partial p} \left[\frac{1}{2p} e^{\frac{(c^2-b^2)}{4p}} J_0\left(\frac{bc}{2p}\right) \right], \quad (22)$$

with

$$p = 2\alpha, \quad c = 2\alpha y, \quad b = y, \quad \frac{(c^2-b^2)}{4p} = y^2 \left(\frac{\alpha}{2} - \frac{1}{8\alpha} \right), \quad \frac{bc}{2p} = \frac{y^2}{2}. \quad (23)$$

In the same way, we obtained

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^{\infty} dx x^3 e^{-2\alpha x^2} I_{2k}(2\alpha xy) J_{2k}(xy) &= -\frac{\partial}{\partial p} \left[\frac{1}{2p} e^{\frac{(c^2-b^2)}{4p}} J_{2k}\left(\frac{bc}{2p}\right) \right], \\ \int_0^{\infty} dx x^5 e^{-2\alpha x^2} I_{2k}(2\alpha xy) J_{2k}(xy) &= \frac{\partial^2}{\partial p^2} \left[\frac{1}{2p} e^{\frac{(c^2-b^2)}{4p}} J_{2k}\left(\frac{bc}{2p}\right) \right], \\ \int_0^{\infty} dx x^4 e^{-2\alpha x^2} I_1(2\alpha xy) J_0(xy) &= -\frac{\partial^2}{\partial p \partial c} \left[\frac{1}{2p} e^{\frac{(c^2-b^2)}{4p}} J_0\left(\frac{bc}{2p}\right) \right], \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

with the same parameters p , c , and b as in formula (23). Here, the derivative $dI_0(cx)/dc = xI_1(cx)$ was used.

The last but one integral on y looks as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{2k}{\alpha} \int_0^{\infty} dy e^{-y^2 \left(\frac{1}{2} + \alpha \right)} \int_0^{\infty} dx x^3 e^{-2\alpha x^2} I_{2k}(2\alpha xy) J_{2k}(xy) &= \\ = \frac{2k}{\alpha} \int_0^{\infty} dy e^{-y^2 \left(\frac{1}{2} + \alpha \right)} \left(-\frac{\partial}{\partial p} \left[\frac{1}{2p} e^{\frac{(c^2-b^2)}{4p}} J_{2k}\left(\frac{bc}{2p}\right) \right] \right) \Bigg|_{\substack{p=2\alpha \\ c=2\alpha y \\ b=y}} &. \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

The modified Bessel function $I_{2k+1}(z)$ can be expressed in terms of a modified Bessel function $I_{2k}(z)$ as follows:

$$xI_{2k+1}(cx) = \left(\frac{d}{dc} - \frac{2k}{c} \right) I_{2k}(cx), \quad (26)$$

which leads to the integral

$$\begin{aligned}
 \int_0^{\infty} dx x^4 e^{-px^2} I_{2k+1}(cx) J_{2k}(bx) &= \left(\frac{d}{dc} - \frac{2k}{c} \right) \int_0^{\infty} dx x^3 \times \\
 &\times e^{-px^2} I_{2k}(cx) J_{2k}(bx) = \\
 &= -\frac{\partial}{\partial p} \left(\frac{d}{dc} - \frac{2k}{c} \right) \int_0^{\infty} dx x e^{-px^2} I_{2k}(cx) J_{2k}(bx) = \\
 &= -\frac{\partial}{\partial p} \left(\frac{d}{dc} - \frac{2k}{c} \right) \left[\frac{1}{2p} e^{\frac{(c^2-b^2)}{4p}} J_{2k} \left(\frac{bc}{2p} \right) \right], \tag{27}
 \end{aligned}$$

which means

$$\begin{aligned}
 \int_0^{\infty} dx x^4 e^{-2\alpha x^2} I_{2k+1}(2\alpha xy) J_{2k}(xy) &= \\
 &= -\frac{\partial}{\partial p} \left(\frac{d}{dc} - \frac{2k}{c} \right) \left(\left[\frac{1}{2p} e^{\frac{(c^2-b^2)}{4p}} J_0 \left(\frac{bc}{2p} \right) \right] \right) \Bigg|_{\substack{p=2\alpha \\ c=2\alpha y \\ b=y}}. \tag{28}
 \end{aligned}$$

As a result, we can write the last but one integral on variable y as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 MS_3 &= \frac{4}{N} \sum_{\vec{Q}, \vec{\chi}} W(\vec{Q}) \varphi_2^*(\vec{\chi}) \varphi_2(\vec{Q} - \vec{\chi}) e^{iz_2 \sin t_2} = \frac{32\alpha^3 e^2}{\varepsilon_0 l_0} \int_0^{\infty} dy e^{-y^2 \left(\frac{1}{2} + \alpha \right)} \left\{ \frac{\partial^2}{\partial p^2} \left[\frac{1}{2p} e^{\frac{(c^2-b^2)}{4p}} J_{2k} \left(\frac{bc}{2p} \right) \right] + \right. \\
 &+ 2 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial p^2} \left[\frac{1}{2p} e^{\frac{(c^2-b^2)}{4p}} J_{2k} \left(\frac{bc}{2p} \right) \right] \Bigg|_{\substack{p=2\alpha \\ c=2\alpha y \\ b=y}} + \frac{32\alpha^3 e^2}{\varepsilon_0 l_0} \int_0^{\infty} dy y^2 e^{-y^2 \left(\frac{1}{2} + \alpha \right)} \left\{ -\frac{\partial}{\partial p} \left[\frac{1}{2p} e^{\frac{(c^2-b^2)}{4p}} J_0 \left(\frac{bc}{2p} \right) \right] + \right. \\
 &+ 2 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(-\frac{\partial}{\partial p} \right) \left[\frac{1}{2p} e^{\frac{(c^2-b^2)}{4p}} J_{2k} \left(\frac{bc}{2p} \right) \right] \Bigg|_{\substack{p=2\alpha \\ c=2\alpha y \\ b=y}} \\
 &- \frac{64\alpha^3 e^2}{\varepsilon_0 l_0} \left\{ \int_0^{\infty} dy y e^{-y^2 \left(\frac{1}{2} + \alpha \right)} \left(-\frac{\partial^2}{\partial p \partial c} \right) \left[\frac{1}{2p} e^{\frac{(c^2-b^2)}{4p}} J_0 \left(\frac{bc}{2p} \right) \right] \Bigg|_{\substack{p=2\alpha \\ c=2\alpha y \\ b=y}} + \right. \\
 &+ \int_0^{\infty} dy e^{-y^2 \left(\frac{1}{2} + \alpha \right)} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{2k}{\alpha} \left(-\frac{\partial}{\partial p} \left[\frac{1}{2p} e^{\frac{(c^2-b^2)}{4p}} J_{2k} \left(\frac{bc}{2p} \right) \right] \Bigg|_{\substack{p=2\alpha \\ c=2\alpha y \\ b=y}} \right) + \\
 &+ \int_0^{\infty} dy y e^{-y^2 \left(\frac{1}{2} + \alpha \right)} 2 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(-\frac{\partial}{\partial p} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial c} - \frac{2k}{c} \right) \right) \times \\
 &\times \left[\frac{1}{2p} e^{\frac{(c^2-b^2)}{4p}} J_{2k} \left(\frac{bc}{2p} \right) \right] \Bigg|_{\substack{p=2\alpha \\ c=2\alpha y \\ b=y}}. \tag{29}
 \end{aligned}$$

We now will calculate the expression MS_4 of the fourth component:

$$MS_4 = -\frac{4}{N^2} \sum_{\vec{Q}, k, \vec{z}} W(\vec{Q}) \varphi_2^*(\vec{z}) \varphi_2(\vec{k}) \exp[iz_1 \sin t_1 + iz_2 \sin t_2 + iz_3 \sin t_3], \quad (30)$$

where variables z_i and t_i with $i=1,2,3$ are determined by formulas (9). The expression MS_4 can be transcribed as follows:

$$MS_4 = -\frac{32\alpha^3 e^2}{\varepsilon_0 l_0} \int_0^\infty dy e^{-\frac{y^2}{2}} \int_0^\infty dx x^3 e^{-\alpha x^2} \int_0^\infty dz z^3 e^{-\alpha z^2} \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} d\theta \times \\ \times \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} d\psi \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} d\varphi \exp[iyz \sin(\varphi - \theta) + ixy \sin(\theta - \psi) + ixz \sin(\psi - \varphi)]. \quad (31)$$

The integral on angles θ, ψ, φ was calculated taking into account series expansions (17) as follows:

$$\frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} d\theta \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} d\psi \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} d\varphi \exp[iyz \sin(\varphi - \theta) + ixy \sin(\theta - \psi) + \\ + ixz \sin(\psi - \varphi)] = J_0(yz) J_0(xy) J_0(xz) + \\ + 2 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} J_{2k}(yz) J_{2k}(xy) J_{2k}(xz). \quad (32)$$

The expression MS_4 looks as follows:

$$MS_4 = -\frac{32\alpha^3 e^2}{\varepsilon_0 l_0} \int_0^\infty dy e^{-\frac{y^2}{2}} \int_0^\infty dx x^3 e^{-\alpha x^2} \int_0^\infty dz z^3 e^{-\alpha z^2} \times \\ \times \left[J_0(yz) J_0(xy) J_0(xz) + 2 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} J_{2k}(yz) J_{2k}(xy) J_{2k}(xz) \right]. \quad (33)$$

We now will calculate the triple integral with three Bessel functions:

$$\int_0^\infty dy e^{-\frac{y^2}{2}} \int_0^\infty dx x^3 e^{-\alpha x^2} \int_0^\infty dz z^3 e^{-\alpha z^2} J_{2n}(yz) J_{2n}(xy) J_{2n}(xz) = \\ = \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \alpha \partial \beta} \left\{ \int_0^\infty dy e^{-\frac{y^2}{2}} \int_0^\infty dx x e^{-\alpha x^2} \int_0^\infty dz e^{-\beta z^2} J_{2n}(yz) J_{2n}(xy) J_{2n}(xz) \right\} \Big|_{\beta = \alpha}. \quad (34)$$

First of all, it is necessary to calculate the integrals on variables x and z . Following textbooks [8, 9], we have

$$\int_0^\infty dx x e^{-\alpha x^2} J_{2n}(xy) J_{2n}(xz) = \frac{1}{2\alpha} e^{-\frac{(y^2+z^2)}{4\alpha}} I_{2n}\left(\frac{yz}{2\alpha}\right), \\ \int_0^\infty dz z e^{-qz^2} J_{2n}(yz) I_{2n}(cz) = \frac{1}{2q} e^{\frac{(c^2-y^2)}{4q}} J_{2n}\left(\frac{cy}{2q}\right), \quad (35)$$

where

$$q = \frac{4\alpha\beta + 1}{4\alpha}, \quad c = \frac{y}{2\alpha}, \quad \frac{(c^2 - y^2)}{4q} = \frac{y^2(1 - 4\alpha^2)}{4\alpha(4\alpha\beta + 1)} \quad \text{and} \quad \left(\frac{cy}{2q}\right) = \frac{y^2}{4\alpha\beta + 1}. \quad (36)$$

They lead to the double integral

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^{\infty} dx x e^{-\alpha x^2} \int_0^{\infty} dz z e^{-\beta z^2} J_{2n}(yz) J_{2n}(xy) J_{2n}(xz) = \\ & = \frac{1}{(4\alpha\beta+1)} e^{-\frac{y^2(\alpha+\beta)}{(4\alpha\beta+1)}} J_{2n}\left(\frac{y^2}{4\alpha\beta+1}\right). \end{aligned} \quad (37)$$

Triple integral (33) on variables x , y , and z is reduced to the expression

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^{\infty} dy e^{-\frac{y^2}{2}} \int_0^{\infty} dx x^3 e^{-\alpha x^2} \int_0^{\infty} dz z^3 e^{-\beta z^2} J_{2n}(yz) J_{2n}(xy) J_{2n}(xz) = \\ & = \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \alpha \partial \beta} \left\{ \frac{1}{(4\alpha\beta+1)} \int_0^{\infty} dy e^{-\frac{y^2(2\alpha+1)(2\beta+1)}{2(4\alpha\beta+1)}} J_{2n}\left(\frac{y^2}{4\alpha\beta+1}\right) \right\} \Big|_{\beta=\alpha}. \end{aligned} \quad (38)$$

Expression (30) of the fourth component can be reduced to the form

$$\begin{aligned} MS_4 = & -\frac{32\alpha^3 e^2}{\varepsilon_0 l_0} \int_0^{\infty} dy \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \alpha \partial \beta} \left\{ \frac{1}{(4\alpha\beta+1)} e^{-\frac{y^2(2\alpha+1)(2\beta+1)}{2(4\alpha\beta+1)}} \times \right. \\ & \left. \times \left[J_0\left(\frac{y^2}{4\alpha\beta+1}\right) + 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} J_{2n}\left(\frac{y^2}{4\alpha\beta+1}\right) \right] \right\} \Big|_{\beta=\alpha}. \end{aligned} \quad (39)$$

The next expression, which will be partially integrated, looks as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} MS_5 = & \frac{4}{N^2} \sum_{\vec{Q}, \vec{\chi}, \vec{k}} W(\vec{Q}) \varphi_2^*(\vec{\chi}) \varphi_2(\vec{k}) \left[\cos(z_2 \sin t_2) \times \right. \\ & \left. \times \cos(z_3 \sin t_3) + \cos(z_1 \sin t_1) \cos(z_3 \sin t_3) \right], \end{aligned} \quad (40)$$

with denotations (9). In these denotations, formula (40) has the form

$$\begin{aligned} MS_5 = & \frac{32\alpha^3 e^2}{\varepsilon_0 l_0} \int_0^{\infty} dy e^{-\frac{y^2}{2}} \int_0^{\infty} dx x^3 e^{-\alpha x^2} \int_0^{\infty} dz z^3 e^{-\beta z^2} \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} d\theta \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} d\psi \times \\ & \times \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} d\varphi \left[\cos(xy \sin(\theta - \psi)) \cos(xz \sin(\psi - \varphi)) + \right. \\ & \left. + \cos(yz \sin(\varphi - \theta)) \cos(xz \sin(\psi - \varphi)) \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (41)$$

First of all, series expansion (17) of $\cos(z \sin t)$ was used [9]. In this representation, the integration on angles θ, ψ, φ gives rise to the following result:

$$\frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} d\theta \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} d\psi \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} d\varphi \cos(z_i \sin t_i) \cos(z_3 \sin t_3) = J_0(z_i) J_0(z_3), \quad i=1, 2. \quad (42)$$

It leads to the transformation of formula (37) as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 MS_5 &= \frac{32\alpha^3 e^2}{\varepsilon_0 l_0} \int_0^\infty dy e^{-\frac{y^2}{2}} \int_0^\infty dx x^3 e^{-x^2} \int_0^\infty dz z^3 e^{-\beta z^2} [J_0(xy) J_0(xz) + \\
 &+ J_0(zy) J_0(xz)] = \frac{32\alpha^3 e^2}{\varepsilon_0 l_0} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \alpha \partial \beta} \left\{ \int_0^\infty dy e^{-\frac{y^2}{2}} \int_0^\infty dx x e^{-\alpha x^2} \times \right. \\
 &\left. \times \int_0^\infty dz z e^{-\beta z^2} [J_0(xy) J_0(xz) + J_0(zy) J_0(xz)] \right\} \Big|_{\beta = \alpha}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{43}$$

The integrations on variables x and z will now be effectuated taking into account the integral

$$\int_0^\infty dx x e^{-\alpha x^2} J_0(yx) = \frac{1}{2\alpha} e^{-\frac{y^2}{4\alpha}}. \tag{44}$$

Two consecutive applications of it lead to the following result:

$$\begin{aligned}
 MS_5 &= \frac{32\alpha^3 e^2}{\varepsilon_0 l_0} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \alpha \partial \beta} \left\{ \frac{1}{(4\alpha\beta + 1)} \int_0^\infty dy e^{-\frac{y^2}{2}} \left[e^{-\frac{y^2\beta}{4\alpha\beta+1}} + e^{-\frac{y^2\alpha}{(4\alpha\beta+1)}} \right] \right\} \Big|_{\beta = \alpha} = \\
 &= \frac{e^2}{\varepsilon_0 l_0} \frac{256\alpha^3}{(4\alpha^2 + 1)^3} \int_0^\infty dy e^{-\frac{y^2(4\alpha^2+2\alpha+1)}{2(4\alpha^2+1)}} \times \left[(4\alpha^2 - 1) - \frac{(4\alpha^2 - 3)\alpha y^2}{4\alpha^2 + 1} - \frac{\alpha^2 y^4}{(4\alpha^2 + 1)^2} \right].
 \end{aligned} \tag{45}$$

To calculate the MS_4 contribution expressed by formula (39), it is necessary to determine the derivative of the following function:

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\frac{\partial^2}{\partial \alpha \partial \beta} \left(A e^{-\frac{y^2}{2}} J_{2n}(x) \right) \Big|_{\beta = \alpha}; \quad x = y^2 A; \\
 z &= \frac{(2\alpha + 1)(2\beta + 1)}{(4\alpha\beta + 1)} = z(\alpha, \beta) = (2\alpha + 1)(2\beta + 1) A; \quad A(\alpha, \beta) = \frac{1}{(4\alpha\beta + 1)}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{46}$$

In turn, it depends on many particular derivatives divided in three groups. The first group contains mainly the $A(\alpha, \beta)$ function as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{\partial A}{\partial \alpha} &= -4\beta A^2; \quad \frac{\partial A}{\partial \beta} = -4\alpha A^2; \\
 \frac{\partial A}{\partial \alpha} \frac{\partial A}{\partial \beta} &= 16\alpha\beta A^4; \quad \frac{1}{A} \frac{\partial A}{\partial \alpha} \frac{\partial A}{\partial \beta} = 16\alpha\beta A^3; \\
 \frac{\partial^2 A}{\partial \alpha \partial \beta} &= \frac{4(4\alpha\beta - 1)}{(4\alpha\beta + 1)^3} = 4(4\alpha\beta - 1) A^3; \\
 \frac{\partial z}{\partial \alpha} &= \frac{2(1 - 4\beta^2)}{(4\alpha\beta + 1)^2} = 2(1 - 4\beta^2) A^2; \quad \frac{\partial z}{\partial \beta} = 2(1 - 4\alpha^2) A^2; \\
 \frac{\partial^2 z}{\partial \alpha \partial \beta} &= -\frac{16(\alpha + \beta)}{(4\alpha\beta + 1)^3} = -16(\alpha + \beta) A^3;
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{\partial z}{\partial \alpha} \frac{\partial z}{\partial \beta} = 4(1-4\alpha^2)(1-4\beta^2)A^4. \quad (47)$$

The second group contains the derivatives of the $B(z)$ function:

$$\begin{aligned} B(\alpha, \beta) &= e^{-\frac{y^2}{2}z}; \quad \frac{\partial B}{\partial \alpha} = -\frac{y^2}{2} e^{-\frac{y^2}{2}z} \frac{\partial z}{\partial \alpha}; \\ \frac{\partial B}{\partial \beta} &= -\frac{y^2}{2} e^{-\frac{y^2}{2}z} \frac{\partial z}{\partial \beta}; \\ \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial \alpha \partial \beta} &= \frac{y^4}{4} e^{-\frac{y^2}{2}z} \frac{\partial z}{\partial \alpha} \frac{\partial z}{\partial \beta} - \frac{y^2}{2} e^{-\frac{y^2}{2}z} \frac{\partial^2 z}{\partial \alpha \partial \beta}; \\ \frac{\partial B}{\partial \alpha} &= -y^2(1-4\beta^2)A^2 e^{-\frac{y^2}{2}z}; \quad \frac{\partial B}{\partial \beta} = -y^2(1-4\alpha^2)A^2 e^{-\frac{y^2}{2}z}; \\ \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial \alpha \partial \beta} &= y^4(1-4\alpha^2)(1-4\beta^2)A^4 e^{-\frac{y^2}{2}z} + 8(\alpha + \beta)y^2 A^3 e^{-\frac{y^2}{2}z}. \end{aligned} \quad (48)$$

The third group concerns the Bessel functions:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^2 J_{2n}(x)}{\partial \alpha \partial \beta}; \quad x &= y^2 A = y^2 A(\alpha, \beta), \\ \frac{\partial J_{2n}(x)}{\partial x} &= \frac{2n}{x} J_{2n}(x) - J_{2n+1}(x), \\ \frac{\partial x}{\partial \alpha} &= -4\beta y^2 A^2, \quad \frac{\partial x}{\partial \beta} = -4\alpha y^2 A^2, \\ \frac{\partial J_{2n}(x)}{\partial \alpha} &= -4\beta y^2 A^2 \left[\frac{2n}{x} J_{2n}(x) - J_{2n+1}(x) \right] = \\ &= -8n\beta A J_{2n}(x) + 4\beta A^2 y^2 J_{2n+1}(x), \\ \frac{\partial J_{2n}(x)}{\partial \beta} &= -8n\alpha A J_{2n}(x) + 4\alpha A^2 y^2 J_{2n+1}(x), \\ \frac{\partial^2 J_{2n}(x)}{\partial \alpha \partial \beta} &= 4A^2 \left[2n(8n\alpha\beta - 1) J_{2n}(x) + \right. \\ &\left. + A y^2 (1-16\alpha\beta) J_{2n+1}(x) + 4\alpha\beta y^4 A^2 J_{2n+2}(x) \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (49)$$

In the case of $n = 0$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial J_0(x)}{\partial \alpha} &= 4\beta A^2 y^2 J_1(x); \quad \frac{\partial J_0(x)}{\partial \alpha} = 4\beta A^2 y^2 J_1(x); \quad \frac{\partial J_0(x)}{\partial \beta} = 4\alpha A^2 y^2 J_1(x), \\ \frac{\partial^2 J_0(x)}{\partial \alpha \partial \beta} &= 4A^3 y^2 \left[(1-16\alpha\beta) J_1(x) + 4\alpha\beta y^2 A^2 J_2(x) \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (50)$$

As was noted above, we are interested in calculating derivatives (46) and (47) at point $\beta = \alpha$. Since functions $A(\alpha, \beta)$, $B(z)$, and $C(x)$ depend on parameters α and β in a completely symmetric form, there are many simplifications denoted below. They lead to the expressions

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial J_0(x)}{\partial \alpha} &= 4\beta y^2 A^2(\alpha, \beta) J_1(x), \\ \frac{\partial J_0(x)}{\partial \beta} &= 4\alpha y^2 A^2(\alpha, \beta) J_1(x), \\ \frac{\partial^2 J_0(x)}{\partial \alpha \partial \beta} &= 4(1 - 12\alpha\beta A(\alpha, \beta)) y^2 A^2(\alpha, \beta) J_1(x) + \\ &+ 16\alpha\beta y^4 A^4(\alpha, \beta) J_2(x). \end{aligned} \tag{51}$$

Formulas (47), (48), and (49) are required to calculate the derivative of the product of three functions $A(\alpha, \beta)$, $B(z)$, and $C(x) = \{J_{2n}(x), J_0(x)\}$, namely, the expression

$$\left. \frac{\partial^2(ABC)}{\partial \alpha \partial \beta} \right|_{\beta = \alpha}, \tag{52}$$

taken at point $\beta = \alpha$. First of all, we used the representation

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^2(ABC)}{\partial \alpha \partial \beta} &= \frac{\partial^2 A(\alpha, \beta)}{\partial \alpha \partial \beta} B(z) C(x) + \frac{\partial^2 B(z)}{\partial \alpha \partial \beta} A(\alpha, \beta) C(x) + \\ &+ \frac{\partial C(x)}{\partial \alpha \partial \beta} A(\alpha, \beta) B(z) + \left[\frac{\partial A(\alpha, \beta)}{\partial \alpha} \cdot \frac{\partial B(z)}{\partial \beta} + \frac{\partial A(\alpha, \beta)}{\partial \beta} \cdot \frac{\partial B(z)}{\partial \alpha} \right] C(x) + \\ &+ \left[\frac{\partial A(\alpha, \beta)}{\partial \alpha} \cdot \frac{\partial C(x)}{\partial \beta} + \frac{\partial A(\alpha, \beta)}{\partial \beta} \cdot \frac{\partial C(x)}{\partial \alpha} \right] B(z) + \\ &+ \left[\frac{\partial B(z)}{\partial \alpha} \cdot \frac{\partial C(x)}{\partial \beta} + \frac{\partial B(z)}{\partial \beta} \cdot \frac{\partial C(x)}{\partial \alpha} \right] A(\alpha, \beta). \end{aligned} \tag{53}$$

As was noted above, we are interested in calculating derivative (46) at point $\beta = \alpha$. Since functions $A(\alpha, \beta)$, $B(z)$ and $C(x)$ depend on parameters α and β in a completely symmetric form, there are many simplifications denoted below

$$\begin{aligned} A(\alpha, \beta) \Big|_{\beta = \alpha} &= A = \frac{1}{(4\alpha^2 + 1)}, \\ \frac{\partial A(\alpha, \beta)}{\partial x} \Big|_{\beta = \alpha} &= \frac{\partial A(\alpha, \beta)}{\partial \beta} \Big|_{\beta = \alpha} = -4\alpha A^2, \\ \frac{\partial^2 A(\alpha, \beta)}{\partial \alpha \partial \beta} \Big|_{\beta = \alpha} &= 4(4\alpha^2 - 1) A^3, \\ z(\alpha, \beta) \Big|_{\beta = \alpha} &= (2\alpha + 1)^2 A; \\ \frac{\partial z(\alpha, \beta)}{\partial \alpha} \Big|_{\beta = \alpha} &= 2(1 - 4\alpha^2) A^2, \\ \frac{\partial^2 z(\alpha, \beta)}{\partial \alpha \partial \beta} \Big|_{\beta = \alpha} &= -32\alpha A^3, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \left. \frac{\partial J_{2n}(x)}{\partial \alpha} \right|_{\beta=\alpha} &= \left. \frac{\partial J_{2n}(x)}{\partial \beta} \right|_{\beta=\alpha} = -8n\alpha AJ_{2n}(x) + 4\alpha y^2 A^2 J_{2n+1}(x), \\
 \left. \frac{\partial z(\alpha, \beta)}{\partial \alpha} \cdot \frac{\partial z(\alpha, \beta)}{\partial \beta} \right|_{\beta=\alpha} &= 4(1-4\alpha^2)^2 A^4, \\
 \left. \frac{\partial B(z)}{\partial \alpha} \right|_{\beta=\alpha} &= \left. \frac{\partial B(z)}{\partial \beta} \right|_{\beta=\alpha} = (4\alpha^2 - 1)y^2 A^2 B(z), \\
 \left. \frac{\partial^2 B(\alpha, \beta)}{\partial \alpha \partial \beta} \right|_{\beta=\alpha} &= \left[16\alpha + (1-4\alpha^2)^2 y^2 A \right] y^2 A^3 B(z), \\
 \left. \frac{\partial^2 J_{2n}(x)}{\partial \alpha \partial \beta} \right|_{\beta=\alpha} &= 8n \left[-1 + 4\alpha^2 (2n+1) A \right] AJ_{2n}(x) + \\
 &+ 4 \left[1 - 4\alpha^2 (4n+3) A \right] y^2 A^2 J_{2n+1}(x) + 16\alpha^2 y^4 A^4 J_{2n+2}(x), \\
 \left. \frac{\partial J_0(x)}{\partial \alpha} \right|_{\beta=\alpha} &= \left. \frac{\partial J_0(x)}{\partial \beta} \right|_{\beta=\alpha} = 4\alpha y^2 A^2 J_1(x), \\
 \left. \frac{\partial^2 J_0(x)}{\partial \alpha \partial \beta} \right|_{\beta=\alpha} &= 4(1-12\alpha^2 A) y^2 A^2 J_1(x) + 16\alpha^2 y^4 A^4 J_2(x).
 \end{aligned} \tag{54}$$

Six components of formula (53) will now be calculated. They are

$$\begin{aligned}
 L_1^{2n} &= \left. \frac{\partial^2 A(\alpha, \beta)}{\partial \alpha \partial \beta} B(z) J_{2n}(x) \right|_{\beta=\alpha} = 4(4\alpha^2 - 1) A^3 B(z) J_{2n}(x), \\
 L_2^{2n} &= \left. \frac{\partial^2 B(z)}{\partial \alpha \partial \beta} A(\alpha, \beta) J_{2n}(x) \right|_{\beta=\alpha} = \left[16\alpha + (1-4\alpha^2)^2 y^2 A \right] y^2 A^4 B(z) J_{2n}(x), \\
 L_3^{2n} &= \left. \frac{\partial^2 J_{2n}(x)}{\partial \alpha \partial \beta} A(\alpha, \beta) B(z) \right|_{\beta=\alpha} = 8n \left[-1 + 4\alpha^2 (2n+1) A \right] A^2 B(z) J_{2n}(x) + \\
 &+ 4 \left[1 - 4\alpha^2 (4n+3) A \right] y^2 A^3 B(z) J_{2n+1}(x) + \\
 &+ 16\alpha^2 y^4 A^5 B(z) J_{2n+2}(x), \\
 L_4^{2n} &= 2 \left. \frac{\partial A(\alpha, \beta)}{\partial \alpha} \cdot \frac{\partial B(z)}{\partial \beta} J_{2n}(x) \right|_{\beta=\alpha} = \\
 &= 4\alpha (1-4\alpha^2) y^2 A^4 B(z) J_{2n}(x), \\
 L_5^{2n} &= 2 \left. \frac{\partial A(\alpha, \beta)}{\partial \alpha} \cdot \frac{\partial J_{2n}(x)}{\partial \beta} B(z) \right|_{\beta=\alpha} = \\
 &= 64n\alpha^2 A^3 B(z) J_{2n}(x) - 32\alpha^2 y^2 A^4 B(z) J_{2n+1}(x), \\
 L_6^{2n} &= 2 \left. \frac{\partial B(z)}{\partial \alpha} \cdot \frac{\partial J_{2n}(x)}{\partial \beta} A(\alpha, \beta) \right|_{\beta=\alpha} = \\
 &= 16n\alpha (1-4\alpha^2) y^2 A^4 B(z) J_{2n}(x) - \\
 &- 8\alpha (1-4\alpha^2) y^4 A^5 B(z) J_{2n+1}(x).
 \end{aligned} \tag{55}$$

There are also six components L_i^0 , with $i = 1, 2, \dots, 6$. They are

$$\begin{aligned}
 L_1^0 &= 4(4\alpha^2 - 1)A^3B(z)J_0(x), \\
 L_2^0 &= \left[16\alpha + (1 - 4\alpha^2)^2 y^2 A\right]y^2 A^4B(z)J_0(x), \\
 L_3^0 &= 4(1 - 12\alpha^2)y^2 A^4B(z)J_1(x) + 16\alpha^2 y^4 A^5B(z)J_2(x), \\
 L_4^0 &= 4\alpha(1 - 4\alpha^2)y^2 A^4B(z)J_0(x), \\
 L_5^0 &= -32\alpha^2 y^2 A^4B(z)J_1(x), \\
 L_6^0 &= -8\alpha(1 - 4\alpha^2)y^4 A^5B(z)J_1(x).
 \end{aligned} \tag{56}$$

The six components enumerated by formulas (55) and (56) give rise to the desirable expression:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{\partial^2 (A(\alpha, \beta)B(z)J_{2n}(x))}{\partial\alpha\partial\beta} \Big|_{\beta=\alpha} &= 4\left[-2n + (4\alpha^2 - 1)A + 32\alpha^2 n(2n + 3)A\right] \times \\
 &\times A^2B(z)J_{2n}(x) + 4\alpha\left[5 - 4\alpha^2 + 4n(1 - 4\alpha^2)\right]y^2 A^4B(z)J_{2n}(x) + \\
 &+ (1 - 4\alpha^2)^2 y^4 A^5B(z)J_{2n}(x) + 4\left[1 - 4\alpha^2(4n + 5)A\right]y^2 A^3B(z)J_{2n+1}(x) + \\
 &+ 8\alpha(4\alpha^2 - 1)y^4 A^5J_{2n+1}(x) + 16\alpha^2 y^4 A^5J_{2n+2}(x).
 \end{aligned} \tag{57}$$

In the case of $n = 0$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{\partial^2 (A(\alpha, \beta)B(z)J_0(x))}{\partial\alpha\partial\beta} \Big|_{\beta=\alpha} &= 4(4\alpha^2 - 1)A^3B(z)J_0(x) + \\
 &+ 4\alpha(5 - 4\alpha^2)y^2 A^4B(z)J_0(x) + (1 - 4\alpha^2)^2 y^4 A^5B(z)J_0(x) + \\
 &+ 4(1 - 20\alpha^2 A)y^2 A^3B(z)J_1(x) + 8\alpha(4\alpha^2 - 1)y^4 A^5B(z)J_1(x) + \\
 &+ 16\alpha^2 y^4 A^5B(z)J_2(x).
 \end{aligned} \tag{58}$$

There are other derivatives on the parameters. First of all, we calculate three of them:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{\partial}{\partial p} \left\{ \frac{1}{2p} e^{\frac{c^2-b^2}{4p}} J_{2k} \left(\frac{bc}{2p} \right) \right\} &= - \left[\frac{(2k+1)}{2p^2} + \frac{(c^2-b^2)}{8p^3} \right] e^{\frac{c^2-b^2}{4p}} \times \\
 &\times J_{2k} \left(\frac{bc}{2p} \right) + \frac{bc}{4p^3} e^{\frac{c^2-b^2}{4p}} J_{2k+1} \left(\frac{bc}{2p} \right), \\
 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial p^2} \left\{ \frac{1}{2p} e^{\frac{c^2-b^2}{4p}} J_{2k} \left(\frac{bc}{2p} \right) \right\} &= \\
 &= \left[\frac{(2k+1)(1+k)}{2p^3} + \frac{(k+1)(c^2-b^2)}{2p^4} + \frac{(c^2-b^2)^2}{32p^5} \right] e^{\frac{c^2-b^2}{4p}} J_{2k} \left(\frac{bc}{2p} \right) -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & - \left[\frac{(4k+5)bc}{4p^4} + \frac{bc(c^2-b^2)}{8p^5} \right] e^{\frac{c^2-b^2}{4p}} J_{2k+1} \left(\frac{bc}{2p} \right) + \frac{(bc)^2}{8p^5} e^{\frac{c^2-b^2}{4p}} J_{2k+2} \left(\frac{bc}{2p} \right), \\
 & \frac{\partial^2}{\partial p^2} \left\{ \frac{1}{2p} e^{\frac{c^2-b^2}{4p}} J_0 \left(\frac{bc}{2p} \right) \right\} = \left[\frac{1}{p^3} + \frac{(c^2-b^2)}{2p^4} + \frac{(c^2-b^2)^2}{32p^5} \right] e^{\frac{c^2-b^2}{4p}} J_0 \left(\frac{bc}{2p} \right) - \\
 & - \left[\frac{5bc}{4p^4} + \frac{bc(c^2-b^2)}{8p^5} \right] e^{\frac{c^2-b^2}{4p}} J_1 \left(\frac{bc}{2p} \right) + \frac{(bc)^2}{8p^5} e^{\frac{c^2-b^2}{4p}} J_2 \left(\frac{bc}{2p} \right).
 \end{aligned} \tag{59}$$

We now will calculate the derivatives on parameter c .

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{\partial}{\partial c} J_{2k} \left(\frac{bc}{2p} \right) &= \frac{2k}{c} J_{2k} \left(\frac{bc}{2p} \right) - J_{2k+1} \left(\frac{bc}{2p} \right) \frac{b}{2p}, \\
 \frac{\partial}{\partial c} J_{2k+1} \left(\frac{bc}{2p} \right) &= \frac{2k+1}{c} J_{2k+1} \left(\frac{bc}{2p} \right) - \frac{b}{2p} J_{2k+2} \left(\frac{bc}{2p} \right).
 \end{aligned} \tag{60}$$

They are required to calculate the second-order mixed derivative

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial p \partial c} \left\{ \frac{1}{2p} e^{\frac{c^2-b^2}{4p}} J_{2k} \left(\frac{bc}{2p} \right) \right\} &= - \left[\frac{(k+1)c}{2p^3} + \frac{k(2k+1)}{p^2 c} + \frac{c(c^2-b^2)}{16p^4} + \frac{k(c^2-b^2)}{4p^3 c} \right] \times \\
 & \times e^{\frac{c^2-b^2}{4p}} J_{2k} \left(\frac{bc}{2p} \right) + \left[\frac{(4k+3)b}{4p^3} + \frac{b(3c^2-b^2)}{16p^4} \right] \times \\
 & \times e^{\frac{c^2-b^2}{4p}} J_{2k+1} \left(\frac{bc}{2p} \right) - \frac{b^2 c}{8p^4} e^{\frac{c^2-b^2}{4p}} J_{2k+2} \left(\frac{bc}{2p} \right),
 \end{aligned} \tag{61}$$

and the expression

$$\begin{aligned}
 & - \frac{2k}{c} \frac{\partial}{\partial p} \left\{ \frac{1}{2p} e^{\frac{c^2-b^2}{4p}} J_{2k} \left(\frac{bc}{2p} \right) \right\} = \\
 & = \frac{2k}{c} \left[\frac{(2k+1)}{2p^2} + \frac{(c^2-b^2)}{8p^3} e^{\frac{c^2-b^2}{4p}} J_{2k} \left(\frac{bc}{2p} \right) - \frac{bk}{2p^3} e^{\frac{c^2-b^2}{4p}} J_{2k+1} \left(\frac{bc}{2p} \right) \right], \\
 & \frac{\partial}{\partial p} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial c} - \frac{2k}{c} \right) \left\{ \frac{1}{2p} e^{\frac{c^2-b^2}{4p}} J_{2k} \left(\frac{bc}{2p} \right) \right\} = - \left[\frac{(k+1)c}{2p^3} + \frac{c(c^2-b^2)}{16p^4} \right] e^{\frac{c^2-b^2}{4p}} J_{2k} \left(\frac{bc}{2p} \right) + \\
 & + \left[\frac{(2k+3)b}{4p^3} + \frac{b(3c^2-b^2)}{16p^4} \right] e^{\frac{c^2-b^2}{4p}} J_{2k+1} \left(\frac{bc}{2p} \right) - \frac{b^2 c}{8p^4} e^{\frac{c^2-b^2}{4p}} J_{2k+2} \left(\frac{bc}{2p} \right).
 \end{aligned} \tag{62}$$

$$MS_3 = \frac{32\alpha^3 e^2}{\varepsilon_0 I_0} \int_0^\infty dy e^{-y^2 \frac{(1+2\alpha)^2}{8\alpha}} \left\{ \left[\frac{1}{16\alpha^3} - \frac{y^2}{32\alpha^4} + \frac{(4\alpha^2-1)^2 y^4}{1024\alpha^5} \right] J_0 \left(\frac{y^2}{2} \right) + \right.$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & + \frac{y^2}{32\alpha^3} J_1\left(\frac{y^2}{2}\right) - \frac{y^4}{64\alpha^3} J_2\left(\frac{y^2}{2}\right) + \\
 & + 2 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\left[\frac{(2k+1)(1-3k)}{16\alpha^3} - \frac{y^2}{32\alpha^4} + \frac{(4\alpha^2-1)^2 y^4}{1024\alpha^5} \right] J_{2k}\left(\frac{y^2}{2}\right) + \right. \\
 & \left. + \frac{y^2(4k+1)}{32\alpha^3} J_{2k+1}\left(\frac{y^2}{2}\right) - \frac{y^4}{64\alpha^3} J_{2k+2}\left(\frac{y^2}{2}\right) \right) \Bigg\}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{63}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 MS_4 = & - \frac{32\alpha^3 e^2}{\varepsilon_0 l_0} \int_0^{\infty} dy e^{-\frac{y^2(2\alpha+1)^2}{2(4\alpha^2+1)}} \times \\
 & \times \left\{ \left[\frac{4(4\alpha^2-1)}{(4\alpha^2+1)^3} + \frac{4\alpha(5-4\alpha^2)}{(4\alpha^2+1)^4} y^2 + \frac{(1-4\alpha^2)^2 y^4}{(4\alpha^2+1)^5} \right] J_0\left(\frac{y^2}{4\alpha^2+1}\right) + \right. \\
 & + \left[4 \left(1 - \frac{20\alpha^2}{(4\alpha^2+1)} \right) \frac{y^2}{(4\alpha^2+1)^3} + \frac{8\alpha(4\alpha^2-1)y^4}{(4\alpha^2+1)^5} \right] \times \\
 & \times J_1\left(\frac{y^2}{4\alpha^2+1}\right) + \frac{16\alpha^2 y^4}{(4\alpha^2+1)^5} J_2\left(\frac{y^2}{4\alpha^2+1}\right) \Bigg\} - \\
 & - \frac{64\alpha^3 e^2}{\varepsilon_0 l_0} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \int_0^{\infty} dy e^{-\frac{y^2(2\alpha+1)^2}{2(4\alpha^2+1)}} \left\{ \left[\left[\frac{(4\alpha^2-1)}{(4\alpha^2+1)} - 2n + \frac{32\alpha^2 n(2n+3)}{(4\alpha^2+1)} \right] \frac{4}{(4\alpha^2+1)^2} + \right. \right. \\
 & + 4\alpha \left[5 - 4\alpha^2 + 4n(1-4\alpha^2) \right] \frac{y^2}{(4\alpha^2+1)^4} + (1-4\alpha^2)^2 \frac{y^4}{(4\alpha^2+1)^5} \Bigg] J_{2n}\left(\frac{y^2}{4\alpha^2+1}\right) + \\
 & + \left(4 \left[1 - \frac{4\alpha^2(4n+5)}{(4\alpha^2+1)} \right] \frac{y^2}{(4\alpha^2+1)^3} + \frac{8\alpha(4\alpha^2-1)y^4}{(4\alpha^2+1)^5} \right) J_{2n+1}\left(\frac{y^2}{4\alpha^2+1}\right) + \\
 & \left. + \frac{16\alpha^2 y^4}{(4\alpha^2+1)^5} J_{2n+2}\left(\frac{y^2}{4\alpha^2+1}\right) \right\}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{64}$$

The MS_i expressions will be supplemented by introducing the imprint coefficients representing the effect of the RSOC.

3. Average Value of Coulomb Interaction Hamiltonian H_{Coul} Taking into Account the RSOC

We now will return to the starting Hamiltonian (8) restoring the imprint coefficients

$S_e(\dot{Q})$ and $S_h(\dot{Q})$. It looks as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \langle \Psi_{bimex}(\varphi_2, 0) | H_{Coul}^R | \Psi_{bimex}(\varphi_2, 0) \rangle = \\
 & = -\frac{4}{N} \sum_{\dot{Q}, \dot{\chi}} W(\dot{Q}) S_e(\dot{Q}) S_h(\dot{Q}) \varphi_2^*(\dot{\chi}) \varphi_2(\dot{\chi} - \dot{Q}) - \\
 & - \frac{4}{N} \sum_{\dot{Q}, \dot{\chi}} W(\dot{Q}) S_e(\dot{Q}) S_h(\dot{Q}) |\varphi_2(\dot{\chi})|^2 \cos(z_2 \sin t_2) + \\
 & + \frac{4}{N} \sum_{\dot{Q}, \dot{\chi}} W(\dot{Q}) \frac{(S_e^2(\dot{Q}) + S_h^2(\dot{Q}))}{2} \varphi_2^*(\dot{\chi}) \varphi_2(\dot{\chi} - \dot{Q}) e^{iz_2 \sin t_2} - \\
 & - \frac{4}{N^2} \sum_{\dot{Q}, \dot{\chi}, k} W(\dot{Q}) \frac{(S_e^2(\dot{Q}) + S_h^2(\dot{Q}))}{2} \varphi_2^*(\dot{\chi}) \varphi_2(k) \exp[iz_1 \sin t_1 + iz_2 \sin t_2 + iz_3 \sin t_3] + \\
 & + \frac{4}{N^2} \sum_{\dot{Q}, \dot{\chi}, k} W(\dot{Q}) S_e(\dot{Q}) S_h(\dot{Q}) \varphi_2^*(\dot{\chi}) \varphi_2(k) \times \\
 & \times [\cos(z_2 \sin t_2) \cos(z_3 \sin t_3) + \cos(z_1 \sin t_1) \cos(z_3 \sin t_3)] = \\
 & - \frac{64\alpha^3 e^2}{\varepsilon_0 l_0} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \int_0^{\infty} dy e^{-\frac{y^2(2\alpha+1)}{2(4\alpha^2+1)}} \times \\
 & \times \left[1 - |b_-|^2 \frac{y^2}{2} - |c_3^-|^2 f(y^2) + \frac{1}{2} |b_1^-|^4 \frac{y^4}{4} + \frac{1}{2} |c_3^-|^4 f^2(y^2) \right] \times \\
 & \times \left\{ \left[\left(\frac{4\alpha^2 - 1}{4\alpha^2 + 1} - 2n + \frac{32\alpha^2 n(2n+3)}{(4\alpha^2 + 1)} \right) \frac{4}{(4\alpha^2 + 1)^2} + \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. + 4\alpha \left[5 - 4\alpha^2 + 4n(1 - 4\alpha^2) \right] \frac{y^2}{(4\alpha^2 + 1)^4} + (1 - 4\alpha^2)^2 \frac{y^4}{(4\alpha^2 + 1)^5} \right] J_{2n} \left(\frac{y^2}{4\alpha^2 + 1} \right) + \right. \\
 & \left. + \left(4 \left[1 - \frac{4\alpha^2(4n+5)}{(4\alpha^2 + 1)} \right] \frac{y^2}{(4\alpha^2 + 1)^3} + \frac{8\alpha(4\alpha^2 - 1)}{(4\alpha^2 + 1)^5} y^4 \right) \times \right. \\
 & \left. \times J_{2n+1} \left(\frac{y^2}{4\alpha^2 + 1} \right) + \frac{16\alpha^2 y^4}{(4\alpha^2 + 1)^5} J_{2n+2} \left(\frac{y^2}{4\alpha^2 + 1} \right) \right\}, \tag{65}
 \end{aligned}$$

where $f(y^2) = (3/2)y^2 - (3/8)y^4 + (1/48)y^6$. The five contributions denoted as MS_iR with $i=1, 2, \dots, 5$ will be supplementarily transformed below. The first contribution to the average value can be transformed as follows:

$$\frac{MS_1R}{\left(\frac{e^2}{\varepsilon_0 l_0} \right)} = - \int_0^{\infty} dy e^{-\frac{y^2(2\alpha+1)}{2}} \left(4 + \frac{1}{2} \alpha^2 y^4 \right) \times$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \times \left[1 - |b_1^-|^2 \frac{y^2}{2} - \frac{3}{2} |c_3^-|^2 y^2 \varphi(y^2) + \frac{3}{4} |b_1^-|^2 |c_3^-|^2 y^4 \varphi(y^2) \right] = \\
 & = -4 \int_0^\infty dy e^{-y^2 \frac{(2\alpha+1)}{2}} + 2 |b_1^-|^2 \int_0^\infty dy e^{-y^2 \frac{(2\alpha+1)}{2}} y^2 + \\
 & + 6 |c_3^-|^2 \int_0^\infty dy y^2 e^{-y^2 \frac{(2\alpha+1)}{2}} \varphi(y^2) - \frac{\alpha^2}{2} \int_0^\infty dy e^{-y^2 \frac{(2\alpha+1)}{2}} y^4 - \\
 & - 3 |b_1^-|^2 |c_3^-|^2 \int_0^\infty dy e^{-y^2 \frac{(2\alpha+1)}{2}} y^4 \varphi(y^2) + \frac{\alpha^2}{4} |b_1^-|^2 \int_0^\infty dy e^{-y^2 \frac{(2\alpha+1)}{2}} y^6 + \\
 & + \frac{3}{4} \alpha^2 |c_3^-|^2 \int_0^\infty dy e^{-y^2 \frac{(2\alpha+1)}{2}} y^6 \varphi(y^2) - \frac{3}{8} \alpha^2 |b_1^-|^2 |c_3^-|^2 \int_0^\infty dy e^{-y^2 \frac{(2\alpha+1)}{2}} y^8 \varphi(y^2).
 \end{aligned} \tag{66}$$

Up till now the calculations were made exactly. Now to avoid cumbersome expressions, we will make an approximation concerning the function $\varphi(y^2)$. We will use the approximation

$$\int_0^\infty e^{-\beta y^2} y^{2n} \varphi(y^2) dy \approx \varphi\left(y^2 = \frac{n}{\beta}\right) \int_0^\infty e^{-\beta y^2} y^{2n} dy, \quad n=1, 2, 3, 4, \tag{67}$$

in which the slowly varying function $\varphi(y^2)$ is extracted under the sign of the integration at point $y^2 = n / \beta$ corresponding to the maximum value of the quickly varying integrand $e^{-\beta y^2} y^{2n}$.

The MS_2R term will now be discussed:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{MS_2R}{\left(\frac{e^2}{\varepsilon_0 l_0}\right)} & = -4 \int_0^\infty dy e^{-\beta y^2} \left(1 - \frac{y^2}{4\alpha} + \frac{y^4}{128\alpha^2} \right) \times \\
 & \times \left[1 - |b_1^-|^2 \frac{y^2}{2} - \frac{3}{2} y^2 |c_3^-|^2 \varphi(y^2) + \frac{3}{4} |b_1^-|^2 |c_3^-|^2 y^4 \varphi(y^2) \right] = \\
 & = -4 \int_0^\infty dy e^{-\beta y^2} \left\{ 1 - |b_1^-|^2 \frac{y^2}{2} - \frac{3}{2} y^2 |c_3^-|^2 \varphi(y^2) + \frac{3}{4} y^4 |b_1^-|^2 |c_3^-|^2 \varphi(y^2) - \right. \\
 & - \frac{y^2}{4\alpha} + |b_1^-|^2 \frac{y^4}{8\alpha} + \frac{3}{8\alpha} y^4 |c_3^-|^2 \varphi(y^2) - \frac{3}{16\alpha} y^6 |b_1^-|^2 |c_3^-|^2 \varphi(y^2) + \\
 & \left. + \frac{y^4}{128\alpha^2} - \frac{y^6}{256\alpha^2} |b_1^-|^2 - \frac{3}{256\alpha^2} y^6 |c_3^-|^2 \varphi(y^2) + \frac{3}{512\alpha^2} y^8 |b_1^-|^2 |c_3^-|^2 \varphi(y^2) \right\} = \\
 & = -4 \int_0^\infty dy e^{-\beta y^2} \left\{ 1 - y^2 \left[|b_1^-|^2 \frac{1}{2} + \frac{3}{2} y^2 |c_3^-|^2 \varphi(y^2) + \frac{1}{4\alpha} \right] + \right. \\
 & + y^4 \left[\frac{3}{4} |b_1^-|^2 |c_3^-|^2 \varphi(y^2) + \frac{1}{8\alpha} |b_1^-|^2 + \frac{1}{128\alpha^2} + \frac{3}{8\alpha} |c_3^-|^2 \varphi(y^2) \right] - \\
 & \left. - y^6 \left[\frac{3}{16\alpha} |b_1^-|^2 |c_3^-|^2 \varphi(y^2) + \frac{1}{256\alpha^2} |b_1^-|^2 + \frac{3}{256\alpha^2} |c_3^-|^2 \varphi(y^2) \right] + \right.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & + \frac{3y^8}{512\alpha^2} |b_1^-|^2 |c_3^-|^2 \varphi(y^2) \Big\}; \\
 & \beta = \frac{4\alpha+1}{8\alpha}; \quad \varphi(y^2) = \left(1 - \frac{y^2}{4} + \frac{y^4}{72}\right); \\
 & \varphi\left(y^2 = \frac{n}{\beta}\right) = \varphi\left(y^2 = \frac{8n\alpha}{(4\alpha+1)}\right) = 1 - \frac{2n\alpha}{(4\alpha+1)} + \frac{8n^2\alpha^2}{9(4\alpha+1)^2}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{68}$$

Making the above approximation with a slowly varying function $\varphi(y^2)$ and extracting it from the sign of integration with different values of $n=1,2,3,4$ as a function of integrand expressions $e^{-\beta y^2} y^{2n}$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{MS_2 R}{\left(\frac{e^2}{\varepsilon_0 l_0}\right)} & \approx -4 \int_0^\infty dy e^{-y^2 \frac{(4\alpha+1)}{8\alpha}} + \left[\frac{1}{\alpha} + 2|b_1^-|^2 + 6|c_3^-|^2 \left(1 - \frac{2\alpha}{(4\alpha+1)} + \frac{8\alpha^2}{(4\alpha+1)^2}\right) \right] \times \\
 & \times \int_0^\infty dy y^2 e^{-y^2 \frac{(4\alpha+1)}{8\alpha}} - \left[\frac{1}{32\alpha^2} + |b_1^-|^2 \frac{1}{2\alpha} + \right. \\
 & \left. + \left(\frac{3}{2\alpha} + 3|b_1^-|^2\right) |c_3^-|^2 \left(1 - \frac{4\alpha}{(4\alpha+1)} + \frac{32\alpha^2}{9(4\alpha+1)^2}\right) \right] \int_0^\infty dy y^4 e^{-y^2 \frac{(4\alpha+1)}{8\alpha}} + \\
 & + \left[\left(\frac{3}{4\alpha} |b_1^-|^2 + \frac{3}{64\alpha^2}\right) |c_3^-|^2 \left(1 - \frac{6\alpha}{(4\alpha+1)} + \frac{8\alpha^2}{(4\alpha+1)^2}\right) + \frac{1}{64\alpha^2} |b_1^-|^2 \right] \times \\
 & \times \int_0^\infty dy y^6 e^{-y^2 \frac{(4\alpha+1)}{8\alpha}} - \frac{3}{128\alpha^2} |b_1^-|^2 |c_3^-|^2 \times \\
 & \times \left(1 - \frac{8\alpha}{(4\alpha+1)} + \frac{128\alpha^2}{(4\alpha+1)^2}\right) \int_0^\infty dy y^8 e^{-y^2 \frac{(4\alpha+1)}{8\alpha}}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{69}$$

The remained integrals equal to

$$\begin{aligned}
 \int_0^\infty e^{-\beta y^2} y^{2n} dy & = (-1)^n \frac{d^n}{d\beta^n} \left(\frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2\sqrt{\beta}} \right), \quad n=1,2,3,4; \quad \int_0^\infty e^{-\beta y^2} dy = \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2\beta^{1/2}}; \quad \int_0^\infty e^{-\beta y^2} y^2 dy = \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{4\beta^{3/2}}; \\
 \int_0^\infty e^{-\beta y^2} y^4 dy & = \frac{3}{8} \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{\beta^{5/2}}; \quad \int_0^\infty e^{-\beta y^2} y^6 dy = \frac{15}{16} \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{\beta^{7/2}}; \quad \int_0^\infty e^{-\beta y^2} y^8 dy = \frac{105}{32} \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{\beta^{9/2}};
 \end{aligned} \tag{70}$$

The next term for calculation is $MS_5 R$:

$$\begin{aligned}
 MS_5 R & = \frac{4}{N^2} \sum_{\vec{Q}, \vec{\lambda}, \vec{k}} W(\vec{Q}) S_e(\vec{Q}) S_h(\vec{Q}) \varphi_2^*(\vec{\lambda}) \varphi_2(\vec{k}) \times \\
 & \times [\cos(z_2 \sin t_2) \cos(z_3 \sin t_3) + \cos(z_1 \sin t_1) \cos(z_3 \sin t_3)].
 \end{aligned} \tag{71}$$

After the previous calculations, this expression leads to the integral

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{MS_5 R}{\left(\frac{e^2}{\varepsilon_0 l_0}\right)^3} &= \frac{256\alpha^3}{(4\alpha^2 + 1)^3} \int_0^\infty dy e^{-y^2 \frac{(4\alpha^2 + 2\alpha + 1)}{2(4\alpha^2 + 1)}} \left[(4\alpha^2 - 1) - \frac{(4\alpha^2 - 3)\alpha}{(4\alpha^2 + 1)} y^2 - \frac{\alpha^2 y^4}{(4\alpha^2 + 1)^2} \right] \times \\
 &\times \left[1 - |b_1^-|^2 \frac{y^2}{2} - \frac{3}{2} |c_3^-|^2 y^2 \varphi(y^2) + \frac{3}{4} |b_1^-|^2 |c_3^-|^2 y^4 \varphi(y^2) \right] = \\
 &= \frac{256\alpha^3}{(4\alpha^2 + 1)^3} \int_0^\infty dy e^{-y^2 \frac{(4\alpha^2 + 2\alpha + 1)}{2(4\alpha^2 + 1)}} \left\{ (4\alpha^2 - 1) - y^2 \times \right. \\
 &\times \left[(4\alpha^2 - 1) |b_1^-|^2 \frac{1}{2} + \frac{3}{2} (4\alpha^2 - 1) |c_3^-|^2 \varphi(y^2) + \frac{(4\alpha^2 - 3)\alpha}{(4\alpha^2 + 1)} \right] + \\
 &+ y^4 \left[(4\alpha^2 - 1) \frac{3}{4} |b_1^-|^2 |c_3^-|^2 \varphi(y^2) + \frac{(4\alpha^2 - 3)\alpha}{(4\alpha^2 + 1)} |b_1^-|^2 \frac{1}{2} + \right. \\
 &+ \left. \frac{3(4\alpha^2 - 3)\alpha}{2(4\alpha^2 + 1)} |c_3^-|^2 \varphi(y^2) - \frac{\alpha^2}{(4\alpha^2 + 1)^2} \right] + \\
 &+ y^6 \left[\frac{\alpha^2}{(4\alpha^2 + 1)^2} |b_1^-|^2 \frac{1}{2} + \frac{3}{2} \frac{\alpha^2}{(4\alpha^2 + 1)^2} |c_3^-|^2 \varphi(y^2) - \right. \\
 &- \left. \frac{(4\alpha^2 - 3)\alpha}{(4\alpha^2 + 1)} \cdot \frac{3}{4} |b_1^-|^2 |c_3^-|^2 \varphi(y^2) \right] - \\
 &- y^8 \frac{\alpha^2}{(4\alpha^2 + 1)^2} \cdot \frac{3}{4} |b_1^-|^2 |c_3^-|^2 \varphi(y^2) \left. \right\}, \varphi(y^2) = \left(1 - \frac{y^2}{4} + \frac{y^4}{72} \right).
 \end{aligned} \tag{72}$$

Using the earlier approximation concerning function $\varphi(y^2)$, we obtain the final expression:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{MS_5 R}{\left(\frac{e^2}{\varepsilon_0 l_0}\right)^3} &\approx \frac{128\alpha^3 \sqrt{\pi}}{(4\alpha^2 + 1)^3} \frac{(4\alpha^2 - 1)}{\left[\frac{(4\alpha^2 + 2\alpha + 1)}{2(4\alpha^2 + 1)} \right]^{1/2}} - \frac{64\alpha^3 \sqrt{\pi}}{(4\alpha^2 + 1)^3 \left[\frac{(4\alpha^2 + 2\alpha + 1)}{2(4\alpha^2 + 1)} \right]^{3/2}} \times \\
 &\times \left\{ \frac{(4\alpha^2 - 3)\alpha}{(4\alpha^2 + 1)} + \frac{(4\alpha^2 - 1)}{2} |b_1^-|^2 + \right. \\
 &+ \left. \frac{3}{2} |c_3^-|^2 (4\alpha^2 - 1) \left[1 - \frac{(4\alpha^2 + 1)}{2(4\alpha^2 + 2\alpha + 1)} + \frac{(4\alpha^2 + 1)^2}{18(4\alpha^2 + 2\alpha + 1)^2} \right] \right\} +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & + \frac{96\alpha^3\sqrt{\pi}}{(4\alpha^2+1)^3 \left[\frac{(4\alpha^2+2\alpha+1)}{2(4\alpha^2+1)} \right]^{5/2}} \cdot \left\{ \frac{(4\alpha^2-3)\alpha}{2(4\alpha^2+1)} |b_1^-|^2 - \frac{\alpha^2}{(4\alpha^2+1)^2} + \right. \\
 & + \frac{3}{4}(4\alpha^2-1) |b_1^-|^2 |c_3^-|^2 \left[1 - \frac{(4\alpha^2+1)}{(4\alpha^2+2\alpha+1)} + \frac{2(4\alpha^2+1)^2}{9(4\alpha^2+2\alpha+1)^2} \right] + \\
 & \left. + \frac{3(4\alpha^2-3)\alpha}{2(4\alpha^2+1)} |c_3^-|^2 \left[1 - \frac{(4\alpha^2+1)}{(4\alpha^2+2\alpha+1)} + \frac{2(4\alpha^2+1)^2}{9(4\alpha^2+2\alpha+1)^2} \right] \right\} + \\
 & + \frac{240\alpha^3\sqrt{\pi}}{(4\alpha^2+1)^3 \left[\frac{(4\alpha^2+2\alpha+1)}{2(4\alpha^2+1)} \right]^{7/2}} \left\{ \frac{\alpha^2}{2(4\alpha^2+1)^2} |b_1^-|^2 + \right. \\
 & + \frac{3}{2} \frac{\alpha^2}{(4\alpha^2+1)^2} |c_3^-|^2 \left[1 - \frac{3}{2} \frac{(4\alpha^2+1)}{(4\alpha^2+2\alpha+1)} + \frac{(4\alpha^2+1)^2}{2(4\alpha^2+2\alpha+1)^2} \right] - \\
 & \left. - \frac{3}{4} \frac{(4\alpha^2-3)\alpha}{(4\alpha^2+1)} |b_1^-|^2 |c_3^-|^2 \left[1 - \frac{3}{2} \frac{(4\alpha^2+1)}{(4\alpha^2+2\alpha+1)} + \frac{(4\alpha^2+1)^2}{2(4\alpha^2+2\alpha+1)^2} \right] \right\} - \\
 & - \frac{630\alpha^5\sqrt{\pi}}{(4\alpha^2+1)^5 \left[\frac{(4\alpha^2+2\alpha+1)}{2(4\alpha^2+1)} \right]^{9/2}} |b_1^-|^2 |c_3^-|^2 \times \\
 & \times \left[1 - \frac{2(4\alpha^2+1)}{(4\alpha^2+2\alpha+1)} + \frac{8}{9} \frac{(4\alpha^2+1)^2}{2(4\alpha^2+2\alpha+1)^2} \right].
 \end{aligned} \tag{73}$$

The next contribution is

$$\begin{aligned}
 MS_3R &= \frac{4}{N} \sum_{\substack{\mathbf{Q} \\ \chi}} W(\overset{\mathbf{r}}{\mathbf{Q}}) \frac{(S_e^2(\overset{\mathbf{r}}{\mathbf{Q}}) + S_h^2(\overset{\mathbf{r}}{\mathbf{Q}}))}{2} \varphi_2^*(\overset{\mathbf{r}}{\chi}) \varphi_2(\overset{\mathbf{r}}{k}) e^{iz_2 \sin t_2}; \\
 z_2 &= Q\chi l_0^2, \quad t_2 = \theta - \psi, \quad \overset{\mathbf{r}}{\chi} = \chi(\cos \psi, \sin \psi); \quad \overset{\mathbf{r}}{\mathbf{Q}} = Q(\cos \theta, \sin \theta).
 \end{aligned} \tag{74}$$

After integration on angles ψ and θ and modulus χ , we obtain the following expression in the special case of the wave function of the relative motion $\varphi_2(x) = (8\alpha^3)^{1/2} x^2 e^{-\alpha x^2}$ with $x = \chi l_0$ and with variational parameter α :

$$MS_3R = \frac{32\alpha^3 e^2}{\varepsilon_0 l_0} \int_0^\infty dy e^{-y^2 \frac{(1+2\alpha)^2}{8\alpha}} \times$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \times \left[1 - |b_1^-|^2 \frac{y^2}{2} - |c_3^-|^2 f(y^2) + |b_1^-|^4 \frac{y^4}{8} + \frac{1}{2} |c_3^-|^4 f^2(y^2) \right] \times \\
 & \times \left\{ J_0 \left(\frac{y^2}{2} \right) \left[\frac{1}{16\alpha^3} - \frac{y^2}{32\alpha^4} + \frac{(4\alpha^2 - 1)^2 y^4}{1024\alpha^5} \right] + \frac{y^2}{32\alpha^3} J_1 \left(\frac{y^2}{2} \right) - \frac{y^4}{64\alpha^3} J_2 \left(\frac{y^2}{2} \right) + \right. \\
 & + 2 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(J_{2k} \left(\frac{y^2}{2} \right) \left[\frac{(2k+1)(1-3k)}{16\alpha^3} - \frac{y^2}{32\alpha^4} + \frac{(4\alpha^2 - 1)^2 y^4}{1024\alpha^5} \right] + \right. \\
 & \left. \left. + \frac{(4k+1)y^2}{32\alpha^3} J_{2k+1} \left(\frac{y^2}{2} \right) - \frac{y^4}{64\alpha^3} J_{2k+2} \left(\frac{y^2}{2} \right) \right) \right\}, \\
 & f(y^2) = \frac{3}{2}y^2 - \frac{3}{8}y^4 + \frac{1}{48}y^6 = \frac{3}{2}y^2\varphi(y^2), \quad \varphi(y^2) = \left(1 - \frac{y^2}{4} + \frac{y^4}{72} \right). \tag{75}
 \end{aligned}$$

Transformations of this expression lead to the next expression containing functions $\varphi_i(\alpha)$ with $i = 1, 2, 3, 4$, or to another one, where the last functions are written in the explicit forms. They are

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{MS_3R}{\left(\frac{e^2}{\varepsilon_0 l_0} \right)} & \approx 2 \int_0^{\infty} dy e^{-py^2} J_0 \left(\frac{y^2}{2} \right) - \int_0^{\infty} dy e^{-py^2} y^2 J_0 \left(\frac{y^2}{2} \right) \left[\frac{1}{\alpha} + |b_1^-|^2 + 3|c_3^-|^2 \varphi_1(\alpha) \right] + \\
 & + \int_0^{\infty} dy e^{-py^2} y^4 J_0 \left(\frac{y^2}{2} \right) \left[\frac{(4\alpha^2 - 1)^2}{32\alpha^2} + \frac{1}{2\alpha} |b_1^-|^2 + \frac{3}{2\alpha} |c_3^-|^2 \varphi_2(\alpha) + |b_1^-|^4 \frac{1}{4} + \frac{9}{4} |c_3^-|^4 \varphi_2^2(\alpha) \right] - \\
 & - \int_0^{\infty} dy e^{-py^2} y^6 J_0 \left(\frac{y^2}{2} \right) \left[\frac{1}{8\alpha} |b_1^-|^4 + \frac{9}{8\alpha} |c_3^-|^4 \varphi_3^2(\alpha) + \frac{(4\alpha^2 - 1)^2}{32\alpha^2} \left(\frac{1}{2} |b_1^-|^2 + \frac{3}{2} |c_3^-|^2 \varphi_3(\alpha) \right) \right] + \\
 & + \frac{(4\alpha^2 - 1)^2}{32\alpha^2} \int_0^{\infty} dy e^{-py^2} y^8 J_0 \left(\frac{y^2}{2} \right) \left(\frac{1}{8} |b_1^-|^4 + \frac{9}{8} |c_3^-|^4 \varphi_4^2(\alpha) \right) + \\
 & + \int_0^{\infty} dy e^{-py^2} y^2 J_1 \left(\frac{y^2}{2} \right) - \int_0^{\infty} dy e^{-py^2} y^4 J_1 \left(\frac{y^2}{2} \right) \left(\frac{1}{2} |b_1^-|^2 + \frac{3}{2} |c_3^-|^2 \varphi_2(\alpha) \right) + \tag{76}
 \end{aligned}$$

Here, the following denotations were used:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \varphi_1(\alpha) & = \left(1 - \frac{2\alpha}{(2\alpha+1)^2} + \frac{8\alpha^2}{(2\alpha+1)^4} \right); \quad \varphi_2(\alpha) = \left(1 - \frac{4\alpha}{(2\alpha+1)^2} + \frac{32\alpha^2}{9(2\alpha+1)^4} \right); \\
 \varphi_3(\alpha) & = \left(1 - \frac{6\alpha}{(2\alpha+1)^2} + \frac{8\alpha^2}{(2\alpha+1)^4} \right); \quad \varphi_4(\alpha) = \left(1 - \frac{8\alpha}{(2\alpha+1)^2} + \frac{128\alpha^2}{9(2\alpha+1)^4} \right); \\
 p & = \frac{(2\alpha+1)^2}{8\alpha}. \tag{77}
 \end{aligned}$$

Introducing the explicit expressions of functions $\varphi_i(\alpha)$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{MS_3R}{\left(\frac{e^2}{\varepsilon_0 I_0}\right)} &\approx 2 \int_0^\infty dy e^{-py^2} J_0\left(\frac{y^2}{2}\right) - \int_0^\infty dy e^{-py^2} y^2 J_0\left(\frac{y^2}{2}\right) \times \\
 &\times \left\{ \frac{1}{\alpha} + \left[|b_1^-|^2 + 3|c_3^-|^2 \left(1 - \frac{2\alpha}{(2\alpha+1)^2} + \frac{8\alpha^2}{9(2\alpha+1)^4} \right) \right] \right\} + \\
 &+ \int_0^\infty dy e^{-py^2} y^4 J_0\left(\frac{y^2}{2}\right) \left\{ \frac{(4\alpha^2-1)^2}{32\alpha^2} + \right. \\
 &+ \frac{1}{\alpha} \left[\frac{1}{2}|b_1^-|^2 + \frac{3}{2}|c_3^-|^2 \left(1 - \frac{4\alpha}{(2\alpha+1)^2} + \frac{32\alpha^2}{9(2\alpha+1)^4} \right) \right] + \frac{|b_1^-|^4}{4} + \\
 &+ \left. \frac{9}{4}|c_3^-|^4 \left(1 - \frac{4\alpha}{(2\alpha+1)^2} + \frac{32\alpha^2}{(2\alpha+1)^4} \right)^2 \right\} - \\
 &- \int_0^\infty dy e^{-py^2} y^6 J_0\left(\frac{y^2}{2}\right) \left\{ \frac{1}{\alpha} \left[\frac{1}{8}|b_1^-|^4 + \frac{9}{8}|c_3^-|^4 \left(1 - \frac{6\alpha}{(2\alpha+1)^2} + \frac{8\alpha^2}{(2\alpha+1)^4} \right)^2 \right] + \right. \\
 &+ 2 \sum_{k=1}^\infty (4k+1) \int_0^\infty dy e^{-py^2} y^2 J_{2k+1}\left(\frac{y^2}{2}\right) - \\
 &- 2 \sum_{k=1}^\infty (4k+1) \int_0^\infty dy e^{-py^2} y^4 J_{2k+1}\left(\frac{y^2}{2}\right) \times \\
 &\times \left[\frac{1}{2}|b_1^-|^2 + \frac{3}{2}|c_3^-|^2 \left(1 - \frac{4\alpha}{(2\alpha+1)^2} + \frac{32\alpha^2}{9(2\alpha+1)^4} \right) \right] + \\
 &+ 2 \sum_{k=1}^\infty (4k+1) \int_0^\infty dy e^{-py^2} y^6 J_{2k+1}\left(\frac{y^2}{2}\right) \times \\
 &\times \left[\frac{1}{8}|b_1^-|^4 + \frac{9}{8}|c_3^-|^4 \left(1 - \frac{6\alpha}{(2\alpha+1)^2} + \frac{8\alpha^2}{(2\alpha+1)^4} \right)^2 \right] - \\
 &- \sum_{k=1}^\infty \int_0^\infty dy e^{-py^2} y^4 J_{2k+2}\left(\frac{y^2}{2}\right) + \sum_{k=1}^\infty \int_0^\infty dy e^{-py^2} y^6 J_{2k+2}\left(\frac{y^2}{2}\right) \times \\
 &\times \left[\frac{1}{2}|b_1^-|^2 + \frac{3}{2}|c_3^-|^2 \left(1 - \frac{6\alpha}{(2\alpha+1)^2} + \frac{8\alpha^2}{(2\alpha+1)^4} \right) \right] - \\
 &- \sum_{k=1}^\infty \int_0^\infty dy e^{-py^2} y^8 J_{2k+2}\left(\frac{y^2}{2}\right) \left[\frac{1}{8}|b_1^-|^4 + \frac{9}{8}|c_3^-|^4 \left(1 - \frac{8\alpha}{(2\alpha+1)^2} + \frac{128\alpha^2}{9(2\alpha+1)^4} \right)^2 \right]. \tag{78}
 \end{aligned}$$

We now will transform the contribution MS_4R , which has the initial expression

$$MS_4R = -\frac{4}{N^2} \sum_{\substack{\vec{r} \\ \vec{Q}, \vec{\lambda}, k}} W(\vec{Q}) \frac{(S_e^2(\vec{Q}) + S_h^2(\vec{Q}))}{2} \times \quad (79)$$

$$\times \varphi_2^*(\vec{\lambda}) \varphi_2(\vec{k}) \exp[iz_1 \sin t_1 + iz_2 \sin t_2 + iz_3 \sin t_3].$$

The z_i and t_i variables with $i=1,2,3$ were determined earlier by formulas (9). After the first stage of transformations, we obtained the expression

$$MS_4R = -\frac{32\alpha^3 e^2}{\varepsilon_0 l_0} \int_0^\infty dy e^{-y^2 \frac{(2\alpha+1)^2}{2(4\alpha^2+1)}} \times$$

$$\times \left[1 - |b_1^-|^2 \frac{y^2}{2} - |c_3^-|^2 f(y^2) + |b_1^-|^4 \frac{y^4}{8} + \frac{1}{2} |c_3^-|^4 f^2(y^2) \right] \times$$

$$\times \left\{ J_0 \left(\frac{y^2}{(4\alpha^2+1)} \right) \left[\frac{4(4\alpha^2-1)}{(4\alpha^2+1)^3} + \frac{4\alpha(5-4\alpha^2)}{(4\alpha^2+1)^4} y^2 + \frac{(1-4\alpha^2)^2}{(4\alpha^2+1)^5} y^4 \right] + \right.$$

$$+ J_1 \left(\frac{y^2}{4\alpha^2+1} \right) \left[4 \frac{(1-16\alpha^2)}{(4\alpha^2+1)^4} y^2 + \frac{8\alpha(4\alpha^2-1)y^4}{(4\alpha^2+1)^5} \right] +$$

$$\left. + \frac{16\alpha^2 y^4}{(4\alpha^2+1)^5} J_2 \left(\frac{y^2}{4\alpha^2+1} \right) \right\} - \frac{64\alpha^3 e^2}{\varepsilon_0 l_0} \sum_{n=1}^\infty \int_0^\infty dy e^{-y^2 \frac{(2\alpha+1)^2}{2(4\alpha^2+1)}} \times$$

$$\times \left[1 - |b_1^-|^2 \frac{y^2}{2} - |c_3^-|^2 f(y^2) + \frac{1}{8} |b_1^-|^4 y^4 + \frac{1}{2} |c_3^-|^4 f^2(y^2) \right] \left\{ J_{2n} \left(\frac{y^2}{4\alpha^2+1} \right) \times \right.$$

$$\times \left[\frac{4}{(4\alpha^2+1)^3} (4\alpha^2 - 1 - 2n + 8\alpha^2 n(11+8n)) + \right.$$

$$\left. + \frac{4\alpha}{(4\alpha^2+1)^4} (5 - 4\alpha^2 + 4n(1-4\alpha^2)) y^2 + \frac{(1-4\alpha^2)^2 y^4}{(4\alpha^2+1)^5} \right] + \quad (80)$$

$$+ J_{2n+1} \left(\frac{y^2}{4\alpha^2+1} \right) \left[\frac{4y^2}{(4\alpha^2+1)^4} (1-16\alpha^2(n+1)) + \frac{8\alpha(4\alpha^2-1)y^4}{(4\alpha^2+1)^5} \right] +$$

$$\left. + \frac{16\alpha^2 y^4}{(4\alpha^2+1)^5} J_{2n+2} \left(\frac{y^2}{4\alpha^2+1} \right) \right\}.$$

The MS_4R contribution was transformed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{MS_4R}{32\alpha^3 \left(\frac{e^2}{\varepsilon_0 l_0} \right)} &\approx - \int_0^\infty dy e^{-py^2} J_0(cy^2) \frac{4(4\alpha^2 - 1)}{(4\alpha^2 + 1)^3} - \\
 &- \int_0^\infty dy e^{-py^2} y^2 J_0(cy^2) \left[\frac{4\alpha(5 - 4\alpha^2)}{(4\alpha^2 + 1)^4} - \frac{4(4\alpha^2 - 1)}{(4\alpha^2 + 1)^3} \left(\frac{1}{2} |b_1^-|^2 + \frac{3}{2} |c_3^-|^2 \varphi_1(\alpha) \right) \right] - \\
 &- \int_0^\infty dy e^{-py^2} y^4 J_0(cy^2) \left[\frac{(1 - 4\alpha^2)^2}{(4\alpha^2 + 1)^5} - \frac{4\alpha(5 - 4\alpha^2)}{(4\alpha^2 + 1)^4} \left(\frac{1}{2} |b_1^-|^2 + \frac{3}{2} |c_3^-|^2 \varphi_2(\alpha) \right) + \right. \\
 &+ \left. \frac{4(4\alpha^2 - 1)}{(4\alpha^2 + 1)^3} \left(\frac{1}{8} |b_1^-|^4 + \frac{9}{8} |c_3^-|^4 \varphi_2^2(\alpha) \right) \right] - \\
 &- \int_0^\infty dy e^{-py^2} y^6 J_0(cy^2) \left[- \frac{(1 - 4\alpha^2)^2}{(4\alpha^2 + 1)^5} \left(\frac{1}{2} |b_1^-|^2 + \frac{3}{2} |c_3^-|^2 \varphi_3(\alpha) \right) + \right. \\
 &+ \left. \frac{4\alpha(5 - 4\alpha^2)}{(4\alpha^2 + 1)^4} \left(\frac{1}{8} |b_1^-|^4 + \frac{9}{8} |c_3^-|^4 \varphi_3^2(\alpha) \right) \right] - \\
 &- \int_0^\infty dy e^{-py^2} y^8 J_0(cy^2) \frac{(1 - 4\alpha^2)^2}{(4\alpha^2 + 1)^5} \left(\frac{1}{8} |b_1^-|^4 + \frac{9}{8} |c_3^-|^4 \varphi_4^2(\alpha) \right) - \\
 &- \int_0^\infty dy e^{-py^2} y^2 J_1(cy^2) \frac{(1 - 16\alpha^2)}{(4\alpha^2 + 1)^4} - \\
 &- \int_0^\infty dy e^{-py^2} y^4 J_1(cy^2) \left[\frac{8\alpha(4\alpha^2 - 1)}{(4\alpha^2 + 1)^5} - \frac{(1 - 16\alpha^2)}{(4\alpha^2 + 1)^4} \left(\frac{1}{2} |b_1^-|^2 + \frac{3}{2} |c_3^-|^2 \varphi_2(\alpha) \right) \right] - \\
 &- \int_0^\infty dy e^{-py^2} y^6 J_1(cy^2) \left[- \frac{8\alpha(4\alpha^2 - 1)}{(4\alpha^2 + 1)^5} \left(\frac{1}{2} |b_1^-|^2 + \frac{3}{2} |c_3^-|^2 \varphi_3(\alpha) \right) + \right. \\
 &+ \left. \frac{(1 - 16\alpha^2)}{(4\alpha^2 + 1)^4} \left(\frac{1}{8} |b_1^-|^4 + \frac{9}{8} |c_3^-|^4 \varphi_3^2(\alpha) \right) \right] -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & -\int_0^{\infty} dy e^{-py^2} y^8 J_1(cy^2) \frac{8\alpha(4\alpha^2-1)}{(4\alpha^2+1)^5} \left(\frac{1}{8} |b_1^-|^4 + \frac{9}{8} |c_3^-|^4 \varphi_4^2(\alpha) \right) - \\
 & -\int_0^{\infty} dy e^{-py^2} y^4 J_2(cy^2) \frac{16\alpha^2}{(4\alpha^2+1)^5} + \\
 & +\int_0^{\infty} dy e^{-py^2} y^6 J_2(cy^2) \frac{16\alpha^2}{(4\alpha^2+1)^5} \left(\frac{1}{2} |b_1^-|^2 + \frac{3}{2} |c_3^-|^2 \varphi_3(\alpha) \right) - \\
 & -\int_0^{\infty} dy e^{-py^2} y^8 J_2(cy^2) \frac{16\alpha^2}{(4\alpha^2+1)^5} \left(\frac{1}{8} |b_1^-|^4 + \frac{9}{8} |c_3^-|^4 \varphi_4^2(\alpha) \right) - \\
 & -2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \int_0^{\infty} dy e^{-py^2} J_{2n}(cy^2) \frac{4}{(4\alpha^2+1)^3} [4\alpha^2 - (1+2n) + 8\alpha^2 n(11+8n)] - \\
 & -2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \int_0^{\infty} dy e^{-py^2} y^2 J_{2n}(cy^2) \left[\frac{4\alpha}{(4\alpha^2+1)^4} (5-4\alpha^2+4n(1-4\alpha^2)) - \right. \\
 & \left. - \frac{4}{(4\alpha^2+1)^3} (4\alpha^2 - (1+2n) + 8\alpha^2 n(11+8n)) \left(\frac{1}{2} |b_1^-|^2 + \frac{3}{2} |c_3^-|^2 \varphi_1(\alpha) \right) \right] - \\
 & -2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \int_0^{\infty} dy e^{-py^2} y^4 J_{2n}(cy^2) \times \\
 & \times \left[\frac{(1-4\alpha^2)^2}{(4\alpha^2+1)^5} - \frac{4\alpha}{(4\alpha^2+1)^4} [5-4\alpha^2+4n(1-4\alpha^2)] \left(\frac{1}{2} |b_1^-|^2 + \frac{3}{2} |c_3^-|^2 \varphi_2(\alpha) \right) \right] + \\
 & + \frac{4}{(4\alpha^2+1)^3} [4\alpha^2 - (1+2n) + 8\alpha^2 n(11+8n)] \left(\frac{1}{8} |b_1^-|^4 + \frac{9}{8} |c_3^-|^4 \varphi_2^2(\alpha) \right) \Big\} - \\
 & -2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \int_0^{\infty} dy e^{-py^2} y^6 J_{2n}(cy^2) \left\{ -\frac{(1-4\alpha^2)^2}{(4\alpha^2+1)^5} \left(\frac{1}{2} |b_1^-|^2 + \frac{3}{2} |c_3^-|^2 \varphi_3(\alpha) \right) + \right. \\
 & \left. + \frac{4\alpha}{(4\alpha^2+1)^4} [5-4\alpha^2+4n(1-4\alpha^2)] \left(\frac{1}{8} |b_1^-|^4 + \frac{9}{8} |c_3^-|^4 \varphi_3^2(\alpha) \right) \right\} - \\
 & -2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \int_0^{\infty} dy e^{-py^2} y^8 J_{2n}(cy^2) \frac{(1-4\alpha^2)^2}{(4\alpha^2+1)^5} \left(\frac{1}{8} |b_1^-|^4 + \frac{9}{8} |c_3^-|^4 \varphi_4^2(\alpha) \right) -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & -2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \int_0^{\infty} dy e^{-py^2} y^2 J_{2n+1}(cy^2) \frac{4[1-16\alpha^2(n+1)]}{(4\alpha^2+1)^4} - \\
 & -2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \int_0^{\infty} dy e^{-py^2} y^4 J_{2n+1}(cy^2) \times \\
 & \times \left\{ \frac{8\alpha(4\alpha^2-1)}{(4\alpha^2+1)^5} - \frac{4[1-16\alpha^2(n+1)]}{(4\alpha^2+1)^4} \left(\frac{1}{2} |b_1^-|^2 + \frac{3}{2} |c_3^-|^2 \varphi_2(\alpha) \right) \right\} - \\
 & -2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \int_0^{\infty} dy e^{-py^2} y^6 J_{2n+1}(cy^2) \times \left\{ -\frac{8\alpha(4\alpha^2-1)}{(4\alpha^2+1)^5} \left(\frac{1}{2} |b_1^-|^2 + \frac{3}{2} |c_3^-|^2 \varphi_3(\alpha) \right) + \right. \\
 & \left. + \frac{4[1-16\alpha^2(n+1)]}{(4\alpha^2+1)^4} \left(\frac{1}{8} |b_1^-|^4 + \frac{9}{8} |c_3^-|^4 \varphi_3^2(\alpha) \right) \right\} - \\
 & -2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \int_0^{\infty} dy e^{-py^2} y^8 J_{2n+1}(cy^2) \frac{8\alpha(4\alpha^2-1)}{(4\alpha^2+1)^5} \left(\frac{1}{8} |b_1^-|^4 + \frac{9}{8} |c_3^-|^4 \varphi_4^2(\alpha) \right) - \\
 & -2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \int_0^{\infty} dy e^{-py^2} y^4 J_{2n+2}(cy^2) \frac{16\alpha^2}{(4\alpha^2+1)^5} + \\
 & + 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \int_0^{\infty} dy e^{-py^2} y^6 J_{2n+2}(cy^2) \frac{16\alpha^2}{(4\alpha^2+1)^5} \left(\frac{1}{2} |b_1^-|^2 + \frac{3}{2} |c_3^-|^2 \varphi_3(\alpha) \right) - \\
 & -2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \int_0^{\infty} dy e^{-py^2} y^8 J_{2n+2}(cy^2) \frac{16\alpha^2}{(4\alpha^2+1)^5} \left(\frac{1}{8} |b_1^-|^4 + \frac{9}{8} |c_3^-|^4 \varphi_4^2(\alpha) \right). \tag{81}
 \end{aligned}$$

Here, parameters p and c and functions $\varphi_i(\alpha)$ are determined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 p &= \frac{(2\alpha+1)^2}{2(4\alpha^2+1)}; \quad c = \frac{1}{4\alpha^2+1}; \quad \varphi_1(\alpha) = \left(1 - \frac{(4\alpha^2+1)}{2(2\alpha+1)^2} + \frac{(4\alpha^2+1)^2}{18(2\alpha+1)^4} \right); \\
 \varphi_2(\alpha) &= \left(1 - \frac{(4\alpha^2+1)}{(2\alpha+1)^2} + \frac{2(4\alpha^2+1)^2}{9(2\alpha+1)^4} \right); \quad \varphi_3(\alpha) = \left(1 - \frac{3(4\alpha^2+1)}{2(2\alpha+1)^2} + \frac{(4\alpha^2+1)^2}{2(2\alpha+1)^4} \right); \\
 \varphi_4(\alpha) &= \left(1 - \frac{2(4\alpha^2+1)}{(2\alpha+1)^2} + \frac{8(4\alpha^2+1)^2}{9(2\alpha+1)^4} \right). \tag{82}
 \end{aligned}$$

4. Conclusions

The lowest spinor-type wave functions of electrons and holes were used to construct the one and two magnetoexciton wave functions, determine their normalization conditions, and deduce the Hamiltonian of the Coulomb electron–electron interaction in the presence of the RSOC. It contains imprint factors, the difference of which determines the affinities of the e–h pairs to interact between themselves.

The existence or absence of bound molecular states formed by two 2D magnetoexcitons can be definitively affirmed only after careful numerical calculations following the deduced analytical formulas. These calculations are in progress.

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